

1 *Review*

2 Clues to Long COVID Linked to Virulence and Infectivity 3 Found in Shell Proteins

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Highlights

What are the main findings?

- The abnormally hard M, detected among all SARS-CoV-2 viruses using AI, is believed to be the cause of SARS-CoV-2 high infectivity as it is more resistance to salivary and mucosal antimicrobial enzymes and, thereby, forces the infected person to shed much greater quantities of viral particles.
- Antimicrobial enzymes can be found also in phagocytes such as macrophages, and organisms such as bacteria and viruses resistant to such such enzymes are known to reside inside the phagocytes.
- Correlations between the inner shell (N) disorder and virulence have been found as greater N disorder allows for for more efficient viral replication via more efficient protein-protein binding and recognition.

What are the implications of the main findings

- Current knowledge of physiology, immunology and biochemistry suggests that the abnormally hard M is not just associated with infectivity but also long COVID as the virus could resist the antimicrobial enzymes in phagocyte and is thus able to dwell in it, which could become a virus reservoir.
- N disorder could modulate the severity of COVID-19 and long COVID by allowing faster replication of the virus.
- An understanding of the mechanisms by which the virus hides in the body, could lead to better treatment of long COVID by targeting the reservoir via antiviral drugs or correctly timed vaccination using an appropriate vaccine version.

Abstract:

Clinical, experimental, and computational evidence of COVID-19 virulence and infectivity has been linked to SARS-CoV-2 shell disorder. A strong link was first discovered using an AI disorder-predicting tool, which detected an unusually hard (low disorder) outer shell among all SARS-CoV-2-related viruses but not in the 2003 SARS-CoV-1. This could account for the high infectivity found in SARS-CoV-2—but not in SARS-CoV-1—as it is believed that hard shells protect viral particles from the onslaught of the antimicrobial enzymes present in the respiratory system and saliva. As a result, much larger quantities of particles are shed by COVID-19 patients. Abnormally hard outer shells (M) are associated with burrowing animals, e.g., pangolins, and SARS-CoV-2 likely acquired these shells due to its long-term evolutionary interactions with pangolins. As for virulence, the inner shell of SARS-CoV-2 (N) has been found to exhibit lower disorder than that of SARS-CoV-1. This lower disorder is consistent with the fact that SARS-CoV-2 is less virulent than SARS-CoV-1, as higher disorder in the inner shell is associated with more efficient protein–protein binding during replication. The link between N/M disorder and virulence or infectivity falls under the umbrella of shell disorder models (SDMs), which can connect virulence, infectivity, and long COVID under one coherent concept. Evidence of the reliability and reproducibility of SDMs as applied to COVID-19 is examined. The hard M that is resisting the antimicrobial enzymes in the respiratory system can be extended to immunological enzymes, especially those found in phagocytes such as macrophages, which can therefore become a reservoir for the virus.

Keywords: coronavirus; COVID-19; intrinsic disorder; membrane; nucleocapsid; nucleoprotein; Omicron; pangolin; shell; virulence; long COVID; attenuation; variant; immune; perforin; complement system; macrophage; virulence, infectivity; pathogenesis; reservoir; Artificial Intelligence; AI; hard shell; lysosome; unstructured; NL63; spike; phagocyte; monocyte; neutrophil

Abbreviations:

COVID-19: coronavirus disease; CoV: coronavirus; SARS: severe acute respiratory syndrome; HCoV: human coronavirus; SDM: shell disorder model; PONDR[®]-VLXT: predictor of natural disordered regions using VLXT; PID: percentage of intrinsic disorder (number of disordered residues divided by the total number of residues); Pang2017: SARS-CoV-2-related pangolin-CoV isolated in 2017; Pang2019: Pangolin-CoV isolated in 2019; N: nucleocapsid protein; M: membrane protein; S: spike protein; SARS-CoV-2, BANAL: SARS-CoV-2-related Bat-CoVs found in Laos; NL63: a common HCoV; RaTG13: a SARS-CoV-2-related bat-CoV discovered in Yunnan; AI: artificial intelligence; EBOV: Ebola virus; NiV: Nipah virus; DENV: dengue virus; HIV: human immunodeficiency virus; YFV: yellow fever virus; ZIKV: Zika virus.

1. Introduction

1.1 Goals and Overview

As COVID-19 (coronavirus disease 2019) [1-3] has already become endemic, many questions remain not fully answered. These include enigmas pertaining to infectivity, virulence, and long COVID, such as the following: What are the underlying causes of infectivity, virulence, and long COVID? How are they linked together? Why is long COVID manifested differently from long SARS (2003 SARS-CoV-1)? What is the source of the virus reservoir in long COVID? This review focuses on the application of the concept of intrinsic protein disorder to COVID-19 and, more specifically, on three closely related models—SDMs (shell disorder models)—that use AI to detect protein disorder, encompassing a variety of viruses [4]. The models link shell disorder to infectivity, virulence, and, potentially, long COVID coherently under one concept. SDMs examine the effects of intrinsic protein disorder with respect to shell proteins, i.e., M (outer shell protein) and N (inner shell protein), in the case of SARS-CoV01/2, investigating the behavior of the virus and its manifestation. While greater N disorder affects the infectivity of the virus by producing more viral particles as greater disorder allows more efficient protein–protein binding, a peculiar phenomenon is detected in all SARS-CoV-2-related viruses, but not SARS-CoV-1. They have an unusually hard outer shell (M) that is seldom seen among CoVs, except those associated with a burrowing animal, such as rabbits and pangolins. This observation leads to the belief that COVID-19 patients can shed much larger quantities of viral particles despite SARS-CoV-2 having lower N disorder than SARS-CoV-1. SARS-CoV-2 appears to achieve this by having a harder M (lower M disorder) that allows greater viral shedding due to its ability to resist the onslaught of antimicrobial enzymes found in the respiratory system and saliva. This paradigm has important implications for long COVID since many of the immunologically related enzymes—especially those found in phagocytes, such as macrophages—are involved in similar chemical mechanisms as those of the respiratory and salivary enzymes. This could provide clues that could help resolve the ongoing mystery in the search for the source of a virus reservoir in long COVID. The case for SDMs as applied to M and N is presented. Computational, experimental, and clinical evidence is examined, with an emphasis on reproducibility and reliability.

1.2 Pangolin Footprints: Enigmas of COVID-19-Related Viruses

It has been more than 4 years since the first outbreak of COVID-19 [1-3]. Even as we are only beginning to understand COVID-19 uncertainties, there is still

123 much to be uncovered and resolved. For instance, why is SARS-CoV-2 highly
124 contagious in contrast to 2003 SARS-CoV (SARS-CoV-1, SARS: severe acute
125 respiratory syndrome; CoV: coronavirus)? The total number of people infected
126 thus far is more than 700 million [3], whereas there were only about 10,000
127 cases in the 2002-3 SARS outbreak [4]. Why is SARS-Co-2 less virulent and
128 much more infectious than SARS-CoV-1? What are the structural differences
129 responsible for the differences? What is the cause of long COVID? Early in the
130 outbreak, it was believed that the reason for the extraordinary contagiousness
131 of COVID-19 lies solely in the spike (S) protein [9-12]. This study re-examines
132 the roles of two highly important, although less-researched, proteins—M and
133 N—while keeping the functions of S in mind.

134 The framework of many studies was established using an AI tool to study
135 the sequence of the M and N proteins. One important but peculiar discovery
136 using the protein disorder AI tool PONDR[®]-VLXT [13-17] is that all SARS-
137 CoV-2-related viruses—not only SARS-CoV-2—have among the hardest outer
138 shells (low M disorder) known within the CoV family [18-21]. It is believed that
139 it is this anomaly pertaining to M that is primarily responsible for the high
140 contagiousness of COVID-19, since a harder M provides greater resistance for
141 the virus against the large array of antimicrobial enzymes present in the saliva
142 and mucus [21-28], thus making it more likely for the host to shed much more
143 infectious particles [29]. N, on the other hand, could help modulate infectivity
144 and virulence, as greater N disorder allows for more efficient protein-
145 protein/RNA/lipid binding [4,16,30-33], which could result in the more rapid
146 replication of the virus, especially in vital organs [34-40].

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148 A retrospective search after the initial COVID-19 outbreak yielded a bat-
149 CoV sample (RaTG13) obtained from a Yunnan cave in 2013 that shared 96.4%
150 genetic identity with SARS-CoV-2 [4-43]. Furthermore, two sets of pangolin-
151 CoVs—obtained from pangolins confiscated by customs in Guangxi (GX) and
152 Guangdong (GD) provinces during 2017-18 (Pang2017 and Pang2018) and 2019
153 (Pang2019), respectively—have approximately 90% genetic proximity to SARS-
154 CoV-2 [44-48]. Later, pangolin samples obtained in Vietnam exhibited similar
155 results [49]. Likewise, a series of COVID-19-related bat-CoVs (BANAL) were
156 found in Laos [50-51]. In fact, one of the samples, BANAL-52, exhibited even
157 greater genetic proximity (96.8%) to SARS-CoV-2 than that observed between
158 RaTG13 and SARS-CoV-2.

159 A search for similarly hard M yielded CoVs associated with burrowing
160 animals, such as rabbits. This enigmatic association explains the true intimate
161 relationship between all COVID-19-related viruses and pangolin-CoVs since
162 pangolins are also burrowing animals [4,18-20,52-54]. The hard outer shell (M)
163 is necessary as the virus must be able to survive longer in buried feces before
164 further transmission.

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166 While most scientists believe that COVID-19 is the result of a zoonotic
167 spillover, a better understanding of its evolution helps. The knowledge of N
168 and M proteins can render our understanding of this evolution more complete,
169 as it bridges the relationship between SARS-CoV-2 and pangolin-CoV. The
170 relationship, as evidenced by the pangolin's molecular "footprints", can
171 account for COVID-19 behavior. The implications of this relationship will be
172 revisited in greater detail later.

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177 One odd characteristic found in all SARS-CoV-2-related viruses and their
178 variants found thus far is the unusually hard outer shell (low M disorder),
179 which is typically found only in CoV associated with a burrowing animal. This
180 hallmark is one of the "pangolin footprints" found in all COVID-19-related
181 viruses discovered so far. The other set of footprints involves attenuations
182 associated with the lower N disorder observed in Pang2017 and later in the
183 Omicron variant [18-20,52-56]. The harder inner shell (N), especially in
184 Pang2017, may also reflect N's ability to protect viral RNA in buried feces,
185 similarly to M [52,55].

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187 Evidence of pangolin footprints offers clues that are beginning to uncover
188 many of the COVID-19 mysteries that are still haunting us. These include
189 questions such as the following: why is SARS-CoV-2 substantially more

190 infectious than SARS-CoV-1? Why is COVID-19 highly infectious to this day?
191 Why is SARS-CoV-2 less virulent than SARS-CoV-1? Why is Wuhan-Hu-1
192 much more virulent than Omicron? What is the actual structural cause of long
193 COVID? Many of these questions have remained unanswered, but the study of
194 the M and N proteins is now beginning to provide some answers from one
195 integrated concept, namely, pangolin footprints. We should not be at all
196 surprised by the explanatory prowess of the N and M proteins, as they are the
197 most abundant proteins found in the cell and virion, respectively.
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199 200 1.3 Long COVID

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202 Another major COVID-19 mystery is the presence of long COVID among many
203 patients, i.e., the persistence of symptoms long after recovery [57-58]. Even as
204 progress has been made in research to explain the mechanism and cause of
205 long COVID, it has remained, by and large, a mystery [59-64], especially with
206 regard to the source of a reservoir, if any. In this study, we review a new and
207 novel explanation. This explanation involves the unusually hard M found in
208 SARS-CoV-2 that allows the virus to resist immune enzymes and thus enables
209 the virus to hide in phagocytes. The abnormally hard outer shell M—which
210 protects the virion from the onslaught of antimicrobial enzymes found in saliva
211 and mucus [19-28,40,52]—is also likely to reduce the chances of the elimination
212 of viral particles via actions of the immune system. We examine the literature
213 pertaining to current immunological knowledge that could provide a potential
214 framework for the mechanism of long COVID caused by hard M. SDMs, and
215 thus, the concept of intrinsic protein disorder will be heavily used to gain
216 insight into the potential mechanisms involved.
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219 The abnormally hard outer shell (M), which protects the virion from the
220 onslaught of antimicrobial enzymes found in saliva and mucus [19-28,40,52], is
221 also likely to reduce the chances of viral particle elimination via actions of the
222 immune system. Upon the examination of immunological principles, shell
223 disorder models (SDMs) further pinpoint the exact immunological mechanisms
224 that are likely to be hindered.
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226 227 1.4 Varying Strengths in Evidence Presented

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229 SDMs provide a coherent framework that links infectivity, virulence, and long
230 COVID. Evidence for each COVID-19 aspect will be introduced. An overview
231 of comparative studies of the infectivity and virulence of some CoVs and
232 various SARS-CoV-2 variants—including SARS-CoV-1, bat/pangolin-CoVs,
233 SARS-CoV-2 variants (e.g., Wuhan, Hu-1, Omicron), and NL63—will involve
234 experimental, computational, theoretical, and clinical data. Overall, we observe
235 that, by and large, SDMs consistently and accurately predict the levels of
236 infectiousness and virulence of SARS-CoV-1/2 and their variants based on the
237 measured predicted disorder (PID: percentage of intrinsic disorder).
238 Furthermore, the disorder of M and N can provide a coherent molecular and
239 physiological explanation for virulence, infectivity, and long COVID. The
240 measurement of virulence can be somewhat problematic, as the precision of
241 CFR (case fatality rate) is often questioned, even if it can highlight the
242 difference in virulence between SARS-CoV-1 (CFR~10%) and SARS-CoV-2
243 (Wuhan-Hu-1 CFR~2%) [1-4]. To mitigate this problem, experimental data
244 involving viral titers and cell plaques are also examined [55]. The
245 infectiousness of SARS-CoV-1/2 and its variants is more easily observed
246 clinically by noting the number of infected patients in an area within a period
247 of time. SARS-CoV-2 is, of course, substantially more infectious than SARS-
248 CoV-1 given the number of people each has infected. Clinical studies have
249 shown that SARS-CoV-2 patients shed significantly more viral particles [29].
250 Again, SDMs put forth a novel explanation (i.e., a hard M that is resistant to
251 antimicrobial enzymes in saliva and mucus) that is consistent with our current
252 knowledge of biochemistry, physiology, and virology [18-22,38-41]. Similarly,
253 such reproducibility is reflected in SDMs' explanation of the observation that
254 SARS-CoV-1 is more virulent than SARS-CoV-2, whereas Omicron is less

255 virulent than all previous variants. It should be noted that many of the
256 predictions made are not restricted to CoVs but also apply to a variety of other
257 viruses, including Nipah virus, Ebola virus, and dengue virus (DENV) [34-40],
258 as discussed below.

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260 COVID-19 enigmas can be broadly categorized according to three aspects:
261 infectivity, virulence, and long COVID. Further signs of the reliability of SDMs
262 can be observed when they explain each aspect of the disease in connection
263 with other features in terms of physiology, virology, and biochemistry. It must
264 be kept in mind that the strength of SDMs in terms of reliability and
265 reproducibility is dependent not only on the individual explanation of each
266 aspect of COVID-19 but also on how each aspect is interwoven with the others
267 according to the explanations. Nevertheless, we need to understand that even
268 as all explanations presented in this review offer clues for further investigation,
269 they are of varying levels of strength. COVID-19 virulence and infectivity have
270 been examined and investigated more intensively since the outbreak of the
271 pandemic, and the results of related experimental and clinical data have been
272 carefully studied, even as more direct studies would certainly help. The
273 application of SDMs to long COVID, on the other hand, is still in its infancy, as
274 insufficient attention and resources have been directed to this topic in the past.
275 Therefore, further research is needed on this issue, both by our group and
276 other independent groups. We believe and argue, however, that there is ample
277 evidence—based on research into the mechanisms of COVID-19 virulence and
278 infectivity and our current knowledge of physiology and immunology—to
279 provide a plausible and solid theoretical basis for the role of shell disorder (or
280 the lack of disorder) in long COVID. As we will see, the virus is detected in the
281 blood and throughout the body of long COVID patients; therefore, this offers
282 some support to our suggestions related to the mechanism of long COVID.
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284 While the individual SDM evidence for each aspect is of varying
285 concreteness, the reproducibility of a model should be evaluated based on how
286 coherent and consistent its explanations are with respect to the central concept,
287 which, in this case, is intrinsic protein disorder (or the lack of disorder) in viral
288 shell proteins. It should also be kept in mind that even as phylogenetic
289 evidence is introduced in this study to explain the crucial role of pangolins in
290 the evolution of SARS-CoV-2—which accounts for its peculiar characteristics—
291 evolutionary and phylogenetic studies, such as what is being presented here,
292 usually leave plenty of room for debates. Such analysis is therefore presented
293 as clues towards further research.
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297 **2. The Shell Disorder Models (SDMs): Three Closely Related Models**

298 *2.1 Three Closely Interrelated Models*

299 Three closely related models were developed using the concept of intrinsic
300 protein disorder via AI tools. Intrinsic protein disorder refers to the lack of
301 structure in an entire protein or part of a protein. Disorder is known to have
302 various important functions, especially in protein-
303 protein/RNA/DNA/lipid/carbohydrate binding, and various tools have been
304 developed to recognize disorder regions and disordered proteins. Among the
305 first developed is PONDR[®]-VLXT, which involves the use of neural network
306 AI to recognize disordered residues given the sequence input [13-17]. PONDR[®]-
307 VLXT has been shown to be a highly appropriate tool, particularly when it
308 involves viral proteins of a large variety of viruses, including Ebola virus
309 (EBOV), dengue virus (DENV), Nipah virus, and HIV [4,18-20,34-40,52,-56,65-
310 67]. PONDR[®]-VLXT is especially suited for the study of viral structural
311 proteins, as it is highly sensitive in the detection of disorder in structured
312 proteins [16]. The first SDM was initiated before 2008 when PONDR[®]-VLXT
313 was used to examine the shell proteins of a variety of viruses. A useful number
314 used is the percentage of intrinsic disorder (PID), which is defined as the
315 number of predicted disordered residues divided by the total number of
316 residues in a protein chain [4,65]. A disordered residue is predicted to be
317 disordered if its VLXT score is 0.5 or above. Upon comparisons of the shell
318 disorder of a fairly large number of viruses, it became obvious that the outer

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shell of HIV, especially HIV-1, exhibits an abnormally high average disorder. It was also discovered that HSV and HCV share this similar characteristic, even though it is not as pronounced as in HIV-1 [418-20,34-40,65-67]. Since very few other viruses, if any, have this characteristic, it seems to be related to the ability of the viruses to evade the immune system, resulting in the absence of effective vaccines for the mentioned viruses. This SDM was labeled “Viral Shapeshifting” [4] and became the parent model for two other closely related SDMs, as observed in Figure 1. Given the behaviors of HIV, HCV, and HSV, higher disorder in the outer shell can also be associated with the ability to penetrate hard-to-reach places such as the brain and placenta, as in the case of the Zika virus [34,35]. Protein disorder enhances the efficiency of protein-protein/DNA/RNA/lipid/glycoprotein binding [16,30-33,55,58].

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Table 1. Three shell disorder models (SDMs). SDMs were developed using the principles of intrinsic protein disorder applied to viral shell proteins.

Year of First Publication	Shell Disorder Model	Details
2008	Viral Shapeshifter Model (Parent)	Disorder of shell proteins was measured for a wide variety of viruses. Only very few viruses have been found to have unusually high disorder in the outer shell (HIV-1, HCV, and HSV). There is no effective vaccine yet found for the three viruses.
2012	CoV Transmission SDM	Links between modes of transmission (fecal, oral, and respiratory) and N and M disorder were found.
2015	Virulence–Inner Shell Disorder Model	Strong correlation between inner shell disorder and virulence of a wide variety of viruses, including DENV, EBOV, NiV, and SARS-CoV-1/2.

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Another model was developed and published in 2015 when it was discovered that there is a strong correlation between DENV virulence and disorder at the inner shell protein [34,35]. Similar correlations were found in a large variety of other viruses, including NIV, CoVs, and EBOV [4,34-40,52-56,65-67] (it must be noted that while Figure 1 provides examples from CoVs and DENV, the SDM is by no means restricted to these viruses). The presence of such correlations is related to the fact that the inner shells are often associated with replication in many viruses and because disorder provides for greater efficiency in protein-protein/RNA/DNA/lipid/glycoprotein binding [16,30-33]. These form the basis of the virulence–inner shell disorder model (Table 1).

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Figure 1. Virulence–inner SDM (shell disorder model) [40]. **A.** Shells PID of DENV and SARS-CoV-2. The inner shell of DENV has been found to be correlated with virulence ($r=0.95$) [34,35]. **B.** Correlation between the SARS-related viruses and N PID. The correlation is based on the estimated CFRs of SARS-CoV-1/2 and Omicron. Note: DENV and SARS-CoV-1/2 shells are not correlated. They are placed together for illustrative purposes only.

The third SDM was first published in 2012 [53] before MERS-CoV was discovered in 2013 [55]. The model divided CoVs into three groups, labeled A–C, which can be observed in Figure 2, with group D added during the COVID-19 pandemic [18-20,40,53,55,56]. Group D was not recognized in the initial model because there were very few CoVs that involved burrowing animals such as rabbits and pangolins at the time [4,18-16,52,53]. Before the COVID-19 pandemic, nearly all CoVs available in our database had M PIDs of at least 8% (see Figure 2). The exceptions are the few available CoVs associated with burrowing animals. It was only during the pandemic that it was discovered that all SARS-CoV-2-related viruses have M PIDs lower than 7% (4-6.3%) (see Figure 2 and Table 2). While the statistical differences appear small, in reality, they are not insignificant or trivial, as we will observe later in the case of M, which is the most abundant protein that encases the entire virion. Even small changes will affect the rigidity of the entire shell. This CoV-transmission SDM invokes the same molecular principle that the virulence–inner SDM uses, which involves greater disorder in the inner shell that provides greater efficiency in viral replication. However, the CoV-transmission SDM extends this principle to the fecal–oral and respiratory transmission potentials, showing that respiratory transmission is viable only when sufficient copies of the virus are shed nasally. This results in N being adequately disordered. Multivariate analysis has found a strong correlation between modes of transmission and levels of M/N PIDs, with statistical significance (multivariate analysis: $p < 0.001$, $r \sim 0.8$, $N = 32$).

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Figure 2. CoV-transmission shell disorder model (SDM) CoVs [55]. In groups A-C, the levels of respiratory/fecal-oral transmission are heavily dependent on N PID, whereas those in group D have unusually low M PIDs (M disorder) that are usually associated with burrowing animals such as pangolins. Group D includes all COVID-19-related viruses (multivariate analysis: $p < 0.001$, $r \sim 0.8$, $N = 32$).

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The CoV-transmission SDM categories with respect to SARS-CoV-1 in group B consist of CoVs with intermediate fecal-oral and respiratory transmission potentials. Upon the publication of the original manuscript, the MERS-CoV outbreak took place in 2012-13, when the SDM had to place MERS-CoV in group C, in which the CoVs exhibited higher and lower fecal-oral and respiratory transmission potentials [54]. This prediction has been reproduced clinically and experimentally [4]. It is also known that MERS-CoV has long been entrenched among camels, especially farmed camels, where it spreads easily by fecal-oral means.

3. Pangolin Molecular Footprint as an Evolutionary Link to the Peculiar Characteristics Found in SARS-CoV-2

3.1. The First Sign of a Pangolin Footprint: Abnormally Hard Shells in All SARS-CoV-2-Related Viruses

When the CoV-transmission SDM was first developed and implemented in 2012-13, a strong correlation was observed between N disorder (N PID) and the modes of transmission [4,53,54]. However, statistical calculations detected a small correlation between M disorder (M PID) and the modes of transmission. PID is defined as the number of disordered residues divided by the total number of residues in the protein. Previously, it was not understood why such a correlation existed. It was not until the arrival of the COVID-19 pandemic, accompanied by a flood of data, that pieces began to fall in place. The CoV-transmission SDM was applied to Wuhan-Hu-1 as soon as the M and N proteins became available, with Wuhan-Hu-1 exhibiting N and M PIDs of 48.2% and 5.9%, respectively [14,40,52-55]. Using the original model, the SDM placed SARS-CoV-2 in group B, which is the same group as SARS-CoV-1.

The SDM identified a highly unusual feature of the virus that was seldom observed in our curated database of known CoVs: The outer shell of SARS-CoV-2 is abnormally hard, i.e., it has a low M PID [18-20]. As more data became available, it became clear that the odd hard outer shell was not a feature exclusive to SARS-CoV-2, but it was also observed in all COVID-19-related viruses, as seen in Table 2 and Figure 2. We can observe that the hard M (low M PID < 7%, Table 2) extends to all SARS-CoV-2-related viruses, including pangolin-CoVs and bat-CoVs such as RaTG13 and the Laotian bat-CoV (BANAL). The details found in the tables are also provided in previous studies [52,55-56], and the protein sequences were obtained either from UniProt [69] or NCBI-Protein [70]. The PONDR[®]-VLXT scores were obtained by inputting the sequences into PONDR[®]-VLXT [13-17]. The PIDs (percentages of intrinsic disorder) were calculated as the number of disordered residues divided by the total number of proteins in a protein chain [4,65-67].

Table 2. N/M PIDs and sequence similarities of COVID-19-related CoVs, with SARS-CoV-1 and non-SARS-CoV-2-related bat-CoVs as references [55]. It should be noted that BA1 was the initial Omicron. At least two Delta subvariants have been detected by SDMs.

Coronavirus	Sequence Similarity M (%) ^a	M PID (%)	Accession: UniProt (U); GenBank (G)	Sequence Similarity N (%) ^b	N PID (%)	Accession UniProt (U); GenBank(G)
SARS-CoV-1	90.5	8.6	P59596(U)	90.5	50.2	P59595(U)
Civet-SARS-CoV	90.1	8.6	Q3ZTE9(U)	90.01	49.1	Q3ZTE4(U)
Laotian Bat-CoV	-	6.0±0.2	-	-	48.3±0.2	-
[Banal-52]	98.7	6.3	UAY13220.1	99.3	48.2	UAY13225.1
[Banal-103]	98.7	5.9	UAY13232.1	99.1	48.5	UAY13257.1
[Banal-236]	99.1	4.1	UAY13256.1	99.3	48.5	UAY1326.1
Pangolin-CoV	-	5.6±0.9	-	-	46.6±1.6	-
2019	98.2	6.3	QIG55948(G)	98	48.7	QIG55953(G)
2018	97.7	4.5	QIQ54051(G)	93.8	46.3	QIQ54056(G)
2017	98.2	5.9	QIA48617(G)	94	44.9	QIA48630(G)
				93.32	46.5	QIA48656(G)
SARS-CoV-2						

Wuhan-Hu-1	100	5.9	YP009724393(G)	100	48.2	YP009724397(G)
Delta					47.1±0.5	
Delta1	99.1	5.9±0.01	QUX81285(G)		46.8	QYM89997(G)
Delta2	99.1	5.9	QUX81285(G)		47.5	QYM89845(G)
		5.9		99.1		-
Omicron	-		-		44.5±0.4	UFO692871(G)
Omicron BA1	98.7	5.7±0.4	UFO59282(G)	-	44.8	WIL50325
Omicron XBB	99.1	5.4	WBI50320(G)	98.6	44.2	
		5.9		98.2		
Bat-CoV		11.2±15			47.7±0.9	
RATG13	99.6	4.1	QHR63303(G)	99.1	48.5	QHR63308(G)
Bat 512	35.5	15.3	Q0Q463(U)	29.4	46.5	Q0Q462(U)
HKU3	91	7.7	Q3LZX9(U)	89.6	48	Q3LZX4(U)
HKU4	42.7	16.4	A3EXA0(U)	51.1	48.5	A3EXA1(U)
HKU5	44.7	11.8	A3EXD6(U)	47.9	47.1	A3EXD7(U)

^a Sequence similarity of the M proteins with Wuhan-Hu-1 as the reference virus (i.e., 100% identity). In this column, we observe that the M protein of SARS-CoV-2 exhibits 90.5% sequence similarity to the M protein of SARS-CoV-1. This contrasts with the 89% genome-wide sequence similarity of SARS-CoV-1/2. Similarly, RaTG13 exhibits 99.6% M similarity to SARS-CoV-2, in contrast to the genome-wide 96.4% similarity. This supports the idea that M may be the most conserved CoV protein among all SARS-CoV-2-related viruses, as implied by the abnormal M hardness.

^b Sequence similarity of the N proteins with Wuhan-Hu-1 as the reference virus (i.e., 100% identity). In this column, we observe that the N protein of SARS-CoV-2 exhibits 90.5% sequence similarity to the N protein of SARS-CoV-1.

It was only after the pandemic—which supplied new data—that we recognized the need to add group D, and we understood why group C had initially been overlooked. A retrospective search for similarly low M PIDs can only be found in CoVs associated with burrowing animals such as rabbits [18-19,55]. Because there were very few such CoVs in the public database before the pandemic, the CoV-transmission SDM was inevitably incomplete at that time. According to our previously published studies [19,20], it also became obvious that the hard M was responsible for the high transmissibility among humans by protecting the virus from the myriad of antimicrobial enzymes found in the mucus and saliva [18-20,40,45,52]. As a result, the host will shed large amounts of infectious particles nasally and orally. There is also reason to suspect that the abnormally hard M may play a significant role in long COVID [40], as the host immune system may often have difficulties when destroying and eliminating viral particles.

3.2. Signs of Attenuation: Another Pangolin Footprint

The three SDMs present us with a set of tools that can output a wide range of specific predictions with respect to SARS-CoV-2 and its closely related relatives. Similarly to how SDM's prediction was applied to MERS, the predictions have exhibited consistency when applied to experimental and clinical data. Figure 2 summarizes an example of the application of the virulence-inner SDM to COVID-19 that is consistent with clinical and experimental data. A strong correlation can be found between COVID-19 virulence and N PID. Using the case fatality rate (CFR) as a benchmark for virulence, we can see that the CFR varies with the N disorder (N PID), with SARS-CoV-1 having the highest CFR of about 10%, followed by the non-Omicron SARS-CoV-2 variants and then Omicron (Figure 1B). Even without using CFR, the virulence-inner SDM makes specific predictions about the levels of virulence of SARS-related viruses and SARS-CoV-1. SARS-CoV-1 is predicted to be of higher virulence given its N PID of 50%, followed by Wuhan-Hu-1 (N PID: 48.2%) and the other non-Omicron variants (Delta N

PID~47.1±0.5%). Omicron (N PID~44.5±0.4%) is the least virulent thus far [40,52,55-56]. It should also be known that CFR is just one measure of the link. As we shall observe, it has been complemented with viral titer and cell/tissue studies. The SDMs can pinpoint mechanisms that account for the predictions. In the context of COVID-19 virulence, higher N disorder corresponds to greater viral replication efficiency, as N is intimately involved in the replication process and increased disorder facilitates more effective protein-protein/RNA/DNA/lipid/glycoprotein interactions.

3.3 Pangolin Footprints: Implications and Manifestations

Two important predictions (shown in Figure 1B) that have been reproduced are that Omicron and Pangolin-2017 (Pang2017) are attenuated based on their low N PIDs. This prediction was first mentioned in a publication in 2020 [14] and later reproduced in at least two laboratories. Omicron, however, did not emerge until November 2021. When the first Omicron sequence became available, it was found that the Omicron subvariant, BA1, has an N of 44.7%, which is very close to that of Pang2017 at 44.8% [20,52,55-56]. Similarly to how Pang2017 was predicted to be attenuated, Omicron or, at least, BA1 must be considered attenuated. It was later shown that all Omicron subvariants have similar N PIDs, with the later ones exhibiting even lower values (XBB.1.16, N PID: 44.2%). Both Pang2017 and Omicron have been clinically and experimentally shown to be attenuated with lower viral titers [40,51,74-79]. Interestingly, in contrast, Pang2019's N PID resembles that of non-Omicron variants, and not coincidentally, its virulence and viral titers do not resemble those of Omicron or Pang2017 [80-82].

3.5. Implications and Manifestations: Infectivity and Virulence

Figure 3A summarizes the implications of SDMs and the effects of different N and M PIDs on the manifestation of COVID-19. SARS-CoV-1 (SARS1) has a higher N PID (~50%) and produces more viral particles, especially in the vital organs. However, because its M is not as hard (M PID ~ 9%) [4], it offers less resistance to the onslaught of salivary and mucosal antimicrobial enzymes and produces sufficient infectious particles for viable respiratory transmission. However, SARS-CoV-2 presents a different story. The Wuhan-Hu1 strain exhibits slightly lower N disorder (N PID ~ 48%) but a substantially lower M disorder (M PID ~ 5.7%) [40]. According to SDMs, the virus will replicate well even in vital organs but not as efficiently as SARS-CoV-1. Even though Wuhan-Hu-1 does not replicate in large quantities in contrast to SARS-CoV-1, the patient sheds more infectious particles because the harder M offers more resistance to the antimicrobial enzymes in the saliva and mucus [40,52]. For this reason, Wuhan-Hu-1 is virulent, but not to the degree of SARS-CoV-1. On the other hand, it is substantially more infectious than the latter due to the immense amount of shedding. Omicron presents a different scenario with a similarly low M PID (~5.7%) but much lower N PID (~44.5%). With respect to these, the SDMs predict low virulence but high infectivity, even if lower than Wuhan-Hu-1. All these predictions have been reproduced experimentally and clinically [52,55,71-82].

Figure 3A describes the underlying mechanism of how differences in N and M disorder affect the manifestation of the virus, especially with respect to virulence and transmission. SARS-CoV-1 (SARS1) spreads efficiently via the respiratory mode with greater virulence but not as efficiently as SARS-CoV-2 (SARS2). SDMs attribute these properties to higher N and M PIDs (N PID: 50%, M PID: 9%) in contrast to those of SARS-CoV-2. Figure 3B illustrates the mechanism of COVID-19 attenuation via pangolins, with an analogy from the Nipah virus (NiV) [4,18,32,33,83].

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SARS-CoV-1

SARS-CoV-2 (Wuhan)

SARS-CoV-2 (Omicron)

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Figure 3. Effects of M and N disorder on virulence and infectivity [55]. **A.** Effects of M and N disorder on virus replication. **B.** Effects of the environment on virulence. SARS-CoV-1 produces high quantities of viral particles, especially in vital organs, because of its high N disorder, but by the time they reach the nasal and oral cavity, many have already been eliminated by mucosal and salivary antimicrobial enzymes as a result of its lower M PID. SARS-CoV-2, on the other hand, produces fewer particles in the entire respiratory system, but more particles can resist the antimicrobial enzymes because of their hard M; therefore, its patients shed more particles. NiV is highly virulent when it is spread directly from bats, whereas the variant with pigs as an intermediate host was less virulent. The inner shell disorder of the latter was observed. Similar observations were made for SARS-CoV-1/2.

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634 While Figure 3A summarizes the mechanisms in which infectiousness and
635 virulence are modulated, Figure 3B shows the evolutionary implications of the
636 mechanisms described. The greater virulence of SARS-CoV-1 is likely due to
637 the brief period the virus spent in its intermediary host, the civet cat, before
638 zoonotic transmission to humans. In contrast, the Nipah virus (NiV) is usually
639 highly virulent when transmission to humans occurs directly from bats, as
640 observed in the cases of Bangladesh and India. Meanwhile, the 1999-2000
641 outbreak involved the infection of humans via pigs as intermediary hosts, and
642 the human CFR was approximately 50% compared to the 75% CFR in the cases
643 from India and Bangladesh [4,33,36,83].

644 The finding, discovered via PONDR[®]-VLXT, that the disorder of inner
645 shell proteins of the virus from the Malaysia outbreak was lower than those
646 from the Bangladesh-India outbreak is consistent with the prediction of the
647 virulence-inner SDM and disorder observations of viruses from the same
648 family. The attenuation of the virus occurred during its infection of pigs, in
649 which fecal-oral transmission is the most convenient route in a farm
650 environment. The hardening of the inner shell protein poses several
651 advantages. Firstly, the fecal-oral route does not necessitate higher disorder in
652 its inner shell protein, and greater disorder requires greater energy, which is
653 wasted if not utilized. Secondly, a harder inner shell offers extra protection for
654 the viral genome. Bat CoVs, in general, have higher N disorder, possibly
655 arising from the need for certain levels of respiratory transmission potentials
656 because of the flight behavior of bats. Respiratory diseases, such as avian
657 influenza, have been known to spread between birds during flight [84-87].
658 There is, therefore, no reason to doubt that respiratory viruses such as CoVs
659 can spread between bats during flights. SDMs support this notion with respect
660 to IBV, which is an avian coronavirus; it has the highest N PIDs, and the higher
661 N PID is associated with higher respiratory transmission (Figure 2). Indeed, as
662 we will see later, bat-CoV N PIDs are usually higher than those of most other
663 CoVs.

664 Given the generally lower N PID and thus virulence, it is plausible that
665 the precursor SARS-CoV-2 was deeply entrenched in an intermediary animal
666 host. There are important reasons to believe that pangolins were involved. A
667 smoking gun can be found in the abnormally hard M found in all COVID-19-
668 related viruses, suggesting a burrowing animal. The presence of SARS-CoV-2-
669 related pangolin-CoVs is apparently widespread in Southern China and
670 Southeast Asia, as evidenced by the discoveries of pangolin-CoVs in Guangxi,
671 Guangdong, and Vietnam [42-49]. Figure 3B highlights the pangolin as a likely
672 reservoir, with pangolin-CoVs circulating among bats, humans, and pangolins.
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675 *3.6. Physiological Mechanisms Allow Dichotomy between Virulence and Infectivity:*
676 *Mucociliary Clearance (MCC)*

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678 It must be understood that the CoV-transmission SDM revolves around
679 the need to have a sufficient concentration of infectious particles for the virus
680 to have viable respiratory transmissibility. This can be facilitated by an
681 abnormally hard M, increased disorder in N, or both, since a harder M makes
682 the virion more resistant to damage arising from the antimicrobial enzymes
683 found in mucus and saliva [21-28], whereas a more disordered N could induce
684 more efficient viral replication as a result of more effective protein-protein
685 binding. The latter is again used in the virulence-inner SDM, in which higher
686 N disorder assists the rapid replication of viral particles, especially in vital
687 organs. How do the two factors interact to allow us consistency among various
688 SDMs? Part of the answer to this question is included in Figure 3A, which
689 summarizes how virulence and infectiousness are intertwined. It does not,
690 however, tell the whole story, especially regarding how the physiology of the
691 host helps in the entire process.

692 Knowledge of molecular physiology has allowed us to understand the
693 roles that the respiratory system plays in the entire transmission process.
694 Mucociliary clearance (MCC) or the mucociliary escalator is of particular
695 interest [88-91]. It encompasses a body of knowledge that describes how the

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respiratory system expels foreign bodies, including viruses and bacteria, via a mechanism known as MCC. MCC is a sophisticated network of hairy ciliated cells covered with mucus that transport foreign particles away from the lungs towards the upper respiratory regions for removal, as shown in Figure 4. During the transportation process, the particle is exposed to antimicrobial enzymes in the mucus.

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Figure 4. The mucociliary escalator/clearance (MCC) system. MCC consists of a network of mucus-covered structures found in ciliary cells. These mucus-covered structures push foreign materials away from the lungs towards the mouth and nasal cavity. MCC is absent in the lungs, where mucus is replaced by surfactants. About 2/3 of foreign matter in the lungs is expelled into MCC. The rest are engulfed by macrophages or remain in the lungs.

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The three main types of cells in the respiratory tract are ciliated cells, goblet cells, and basal cells. We know that the ciliated cells are mucus-coated cells with hair-like structures used to move particles away from the lungs, while goblet cells produce the mucus [80]. In contrast, however, the lungs have different types of cells that do not contain mucus. It is likely that the antimicrobial enzymes in mucus and saliva are too harsh for the delicate function of the lungs. Instead, the mucus is replaced by surfactant. The cells found in the lungs are alveolar type I cells (AT1), alveolar type II (pneumocytes, AT2), and macrophages. AT1 secretes surfactants [91-92]. While surfactants are known to have some antimicrobial properties, they are incomparable to the myriad of antimicrobial enzymes found in the mucus.

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Given these physiological mechanisms, we can now understand how the host body modulates the spread and virulence of SARS-CoV-1/2, as seen in Figure 3. When SARS-CoV-1 infects a patient, the greater N disorder allows for the rapid replication of a greater quantity of viral particles throughout the respiratory system. The particles are, however, subjected to MCC, in which the particles are swept upwards towards the nasal cavity, but by the time they reach the nostril, most infectious particles are eliminated or damaged due to the comparatively less rigid outer shell, M. The particles that are produced in the lungs tell a different story. Experiments have shown that the lungs partially participate in the MCC process by pushing 2/3 of foreign particles into the respiratory tract [93]. Since 1/3 of the original particles remain in the lungs, the remaining particles could pose a danger to the patient by damaging the lungs, especially when there are many of them. SARS-CoV-2, on the other hand, produces a more moderate amount of particles throughout the respiratory system, and many of the particles that are transported to the nostril via MCC remain undamaged, unlike in the case of SARS-CoV-1, as the former has an abnormally hard M.

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745 3.7. *Phylogenetic Trees Using M Reveal a More Intimate Relationship Between*
746 *Pangolin-CoVs and SARS-CoV-2: Another Sign of a Pangolin Footprint*
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748 We have seen that a hard M is the hallmark of all thus-far-known COVID-
749 19 viruses. Being hard or ordered usually entails a more conserved protein.
750 Based on this, M is very likely to be highly conserved among all COVID-19-
751 related viruses. Such a feature renders M more ideal for phylogenetic studies,
752 as it is known that recombinations could cause gross errors in phylogenetic
753 calculations. Interestingly, phylogenetic calculations yielded results that are
754 different from those using the entire genome or other proteins [41-48,52,55].
755 Figure 5A,C use M to show that pangolin-CoVs have a much closer
756 relationship with SARS-CoV-2, which is not observed when other proteins
757 such as N (Figure 5B) or the entire genome is used.
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759 Figure 5A is different from Figure 5C as it involves slightly different
760 algorithms. In any case, both show that pangolin-CoVs have intimate
761 relationships with SARS-CoV-2. It is interesting to note that the two viruses
762 that have the greatest sequence similarities to SAR-CoV-2 are bat-CoVs—
763 specifically RaTG13 and BANAL-52 at 96.1% and 96.8%, respectively [51-52].
764 What is intriguing, however, is that in Figure 3A, BANAL-52 and Pang2019
765 have the closest relationship to SARS-CoV-2, in contrast to RaTG13. How can
766 this be when RaTG13 has a 96.1% sequence identity to SARS-CoV-2 compared
767 to about 90% for Pang2019? Sequence identity does not offer the full picture
768 because of the possibility of recombination occurring. Furthermore,
769 phylogenetic genetic algorithms tend to make mistakes when recombination
770 has taken place [94]. The abnormally hard M found in all COVID-19-related
771 viruses entails a structural and genetic conservation, which means that the
772 likelihood of any recombination having taken place is much lower. Therefore,
773 we believe that Figure 5A,C present the most accurate phylogenetic study by
774 avoiding the chances of recombination.
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776 Yet another odd feature can be observed in Figure 5C, where Omicron is
777 more closely related to pangolin-CoVs than to the other variants [40,52,55].
778 While this may seem odd, we know that Omicron itself is shrouded in mystery.
779 When Omicron was first sequenced, it was found to have mutations that are unlike any
780 other variants. The question that quickly arises is this: Where has Omicron been hiding
781 all along [95]? Why did the medical and scientific community not notice it if it was in
782 the human population? There were a few suggestions. A few scientists suggested that
783 the virus was hiding in a small group of immunocompromised people, such as HIV or
784 cancer patients [96]. Others have suggested that the virus had been hiding in an animal
785 such as a rat or pangolin. One study suggested that Omicron had been hiding among
786 mice based on the mutations of its S protein and mouse ACE-2 [96]. Disorder studies
787 on Omicron suggest that it could be hiding in a burrowing animal, such as a pangolin,
788 as the first Omicron variant BA1 had an even harder M than other SARS-CoV-2
789 variants (M PIDs: 5.4% vs. 5.8%) [55]. The idea that Omicron had been hiding in mice
790 actually does not contradict the suggestion in the previous statement, since mice are
791 also burrowing animals. A complication arises, however, when we examine the
792 evolution of mice and rats. While rats and mice dwell in burrows in the countryside,
793 rats and mice in urban settings have evolved to live in human homes (Schmidt-Holmes
794 et al.) [97]. Therefore, depending on the species, they could have characteristics of both
795 burrowing and non-burrowing animals. The phylogenetic tree (Figure 5C) that shows
796 an unusually close relationship between Omicron and pangolin-CoVs, in contrast to the
797 other variants, adds an important clue towards solving the puzzle. The phylogenetic
798 tree suggests that it was literally hiding within a population of a burrowing
799 animal, such as pangolins.
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814 **Figure 5.** CoV phylogenetic study trees using M. **A.** Phylogenetic study of CoVs using M via CLUSTAL OMEGA [89]. **B.**
815 Phylogenetic study of CoVs using N via CLUSTAL OMEGA [98-99]. **C.** Phylogenetic study of COVID-19-related viruses
816 using M (via CLUSTALW [100]). Viruses related to SARS-CoV-2/1 are shaded in blue in (A) and (B) [40].

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4. The Shell Disorder Models and Reproducibility: M and N Proteins

4.1. The Problem with the S Protein: Limitations and Potentials

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When COVID-19 first struck in Wuhan, it spread globally with a ferocity not seen since SARS-CoV-1, despite efforts to control it. Almost immediately, many scientists began to zero in on S as the protein responsible for its high infectivity [9-11]. A computational model suggested that SARS-CoV-2 S binds more efficiently to the ACE-2 receptor than SARS-CoV-1 [9-11]. Furthermore, a specific polybasic sequence known as the furin cleavage site (FCS) can only be found in SARS-CoV-2 but not in the COVID-19-related bat-CoVs, pangolin-CoV, and SARS-CoV-1 [101-103]. Many scientists hailed S, as well as FCS, as the holy grail of COVID-19 transmissibility and virulence knowledge [102-103].

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The S protein has been widely studied [104] since it plays important roles with many implications. It is intimately involved in viral entry, which presents an opportunity for the discovery of drugs and vaccines that block the attachment of the virus to the host cells [104]. Furthermore, being a surface protein, it is widely studied for the way its mutations help evade the host immune system. It is therefore not difficult to see why S is the most studied CoV protein. S is, however, so intensively studied that one might get the impression it is the only protein that matters or that no other CoV proteins exist. This paradigm is, of course, nonsensical as it violates a basic tenet of biochemistry: each protein plays individual but important roles [105].

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Even in the debate involving COVID-19's origin, many scientists seem to imply that the secret of COVID-19 infectiousness and virulence lies in the S protein and that the moment the secret of S is unlocked, the origin of COVID-19 will be uncovered as well [102-103]. Contrary to the popular notion, there is

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845 mounting clinical and experimental evidence that the S protein may not be the
846 main underlying cause of COVID-19 infectiousness and virulence. One major
847 piece of evidence for this lies in a comprehensive clinical study conducted by
848 Wolfel et al. [29]. In this study, it was found that COVID-19 patients shed
849 substantially more infectious particles than SARS-CoV-1 patients. If we look
850 closely, the question that comes to mind is as follows: Why does SARS-CoV-2
851 require substantially more particles to be more infectious if its S has a 10 or
852 1000 times [9-11] greater binding affinity to ACE-2 than the latter? It is
853 important to keep in mind that producing additional infectious particles
854 requires substantial energy, and nature does not generally expend energy on
855 redundant processes. One could, however, attempt to navigate this paradox by
856 claiming that the S affinity to ACE-2 is responsible for the more rapid
857 replication of the virus. Unfortunately, this suggestion contradicts what we
858 know about the life cycle of the virus, as viral entry represents only the initial
859 stage in a long series of events that includes RNA replication, protein
860 production, assembly, packaging, and the budding of viral particles [106-109].
861

862 There are those who suggest that it is possible that SARS-CoV-1 S binds
863 more efficiently to ACE-2 in cells in the lower respiratory tract in contrast to
864 SARS-CoV-2 [12]. There are a number of issues that arise when such an
865 argument is made. Firstly, the argument is made without considering current
866 physiological knowledge, namely, the mucociliary clearance system (MCC),
867 which allows viral particles produced throughout the respiratory system to be
868 transported upwards towards the nasal area such that they can be expelled and
869 shed [88-91]. Secondly, to our knowledge, attempts to reproduce the argument
870 involving SARS-CoV-1 S and ACE-2 have not been conducted experimentally,
871 probably because of the current difficulty in obtaining the now extinct SARS-
872 CoV-1 to conduct comparative experiments alongside SARS-CoV-2. There are,
873 however, also similar arguments made to account for the differences in
874 virulence of Omicron and non-Omicron variants (Hui et al. [78]). The
875 difference is that the COVID-19 pandemic provides us with a deluge of clinical
876 and experimental data. In fact, attempts to reproduce this argument have been
877 carried out, which we will discuss at length later.
878

879 The clinical study of Wolfel et al. [29] is only the tip of the iceberg, as there
880 is also a deluge of other evidence that shows that the nature of S is not what
881 many scientists have made it out to be. Nor does S alone provide for a coherent
882 conceptual framework of COVID-19 infectiousness and virulence, unlike M
883 and N. This is also the case with long COVID. We will examine these in greater
884 detail in later sections. This is not to say that S is unimportant or that it does
885 not play any part in infectiousness or virulence. It is important, but we must
886 also fully comprehend its true potential and limitations. A more complete
887 understanding of the true limitations and potentials of S will come when we
888 study other important proteins, such as N and M, more thoroughly, which is
889 challenging even if the majority of research is oriented towards S.
890

891 *4.2. SDMs and Reproducibility*

892 We have seen that SDMs are highly reproducible due to their ability to
893 accurately predict and explain certain phenomena that are otherwise difficult
894 to account for. Unlike alternative explanations, they are explained in a coherent
895 manner using a logical and unified paradigm that is consistent with current
896 physiology and biochemistry knowledge [52]. There is also important clinical
897 and experimental evidence that reproduces many of the predictions of SDMs.
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899 While a previous experiment was not able to detect any statistical
900 difference in the ability of SARS-CoV-2 to last on various surfaces in the
901 presence of light when compared to SARS-CoV-1, Riddell et al. [21] conducted
902 a similar experiment devoid of light, and they found that SARS-CoV-2 lasts
903 substantially longer on external surfaces than the control CoVs. SDMs predict
904 that SARS-CoV-2 is more persistent than most viruses as its unusually hard M
905 protects against the environment and harsh antimicrobial enzymes, and this
906 experiment reaffirms SARS-CoV-2's resilience in the absence of light.

907 The reproducibility of SDMs is not only confined to computational and
908 experimental research but also extends to clinical studies. One such study
909 involved an investigation into the infectiousness of SARS-CoV-19. It was found
910 that COVID-19 patients shed substantially larger amounts of infectious
911 particles than 2003-SARS patients [29]. This contradicts all other paradigms set

911 forth. For instance, if S is fully responsible and has a much greater affinity for
912 human ACE-2, why does SARS-CoV-2 need to expunge such higher quantities
913 of particles in order to be more infectious? SDMs provide for a substantially
914 more elegant explanation: The virus is more resistant to the salivary and
915 mucosal antimicrobial enzymes because of the abnormally hard SARS-CoV-2
916 outer shell (low M PID). This clinical observation raises more questions than it
917 answers. More specifically, how is the virus able to induce the host to expel
918 such a large number of particles without being more virulent to the body? If
919 we assume that the body is shedding more viral particles because it is
920 producing more virus copies, then vital organs such as the lungs should be
921 flooded with the virus, thus making the latter more dangerous, but this is
922 apparently not happening in the case of COVID-19.

923 Adding to this paradox, Ogando et al. [79] found that SARS-CoV-1
924 exhibits higher viral growth in VERO-E6 cells than SARS-CoV-2 under the
925 same conditions. Even if this is consistent with the greater pathogenesis of
926 SARS-CoV-2, how do we then reconcile this result with the previously
927 mentioned clinical observation? If SARS-CoV-2 S has a 10 or 1000 times [9-11]
928 greater affinity for ACE-2 than the affinity between SARS-CoV-1 S and ACE-2,
929 how is this possible? It seems that we need to look elsewhere for answers by
930 examining N and M more closely. The SDMs explain that the reason SARS-
931 CoV-1 is producing higher levels of particles is related to the higher N disorder
932 that allows greater efficiencies in its replication process; however, conversely,
933 fewer infectious particles are shed by the body as the higher M PID does not
934 provide sufficient protection against antimicrobial enzymes.

935 Yet another enigma involves long COVID [110-111], and SDMs can
936 explain the persistence of the virus among COVID-19 patients even months
937 after infection. Again, we return to the theme of hard M that protects the virus
938 from antimicrobial enzymes. This time, the focus is not only on mucosal and
939 salivary enzymes as in the case of infectivity but also on antimicrobial enzymes
940 in the immune system. Further discussion on the antimicrobial enzymes found
941 in the immune system can be found in the long COVID section below.

942 4.3 More Reproducibility: Omicrons and Pangolin-CoVs

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944
945 There are many other predictions that SDMs make involving N and M.
946 One such prediction pertains to pangolin-CoV. When SDMs were applied to
947 pangolin-CoVs, it became obvious that the 2017 pangolin-CoV (Pang2017)
948 isolate from Guangxi is attenuated because of its low N PID (~44%) [40,52,55-
949 56]. There are several implications for this finding. If this or a similar virus had
950 entered the human population, it likely would have spread quietly among
951 humans as a mild cold, without attracting the attention of the medical
952 community [18]. The predicted attenuation has been independently
953 reproduced by several laboratories [52,55,74-77]. Animal models have observed
954 milder manifestations of symptoms upon Pang2017 infection, in contrast to the
955 Wuhan-Hu-1 strain. The SDM prediction pertaining to Pang2017 was
956 published before the arrival of Omicron.

957
958 Omicron was first detected in South Africa around November 2021.
959 Omicron was clinically and, later, experimentally observed to be milder than
960 previous variants [71-78]. Once again, SDMs offer important insights. Based on
961 the initial Omicron BA.1 subvariant, the N and M PIDs are 43.65% and 5.4%,
962 which are both lower than previous variants [49]. The smaller-than-usual M
963 PID (5.9% vs. 5.4%) could suggest that the virus had a recent origin involving a
964 burrowing animal, whereas the lower N PID predicts that Omicron is likely
965 attenuated to similar levels as Pang2017. The prediction involving N PIDs was
966 experimentally replicated when it was shown that the viral growth of VERO-
967 E6 cells infected by Pang2017 and Omicron is very similar and when it was
968 shown that the viral damage on cells by the two viruses is similar [55]. This
969 presents evidence of further reproducibility for both Pang2017 and Omicron.
970 Omicron has also been shown to be attenuated with lower growth than
971 Wuhan-Hu-1 under viral titration [55,75,77,79].

972
973 The correlations between N disorder and viral titer or virulence can be
974 found in SARS-CoV-2-related virus data that include Pang2019 [71-73,75] and
975 the Laotian bats-CoV (BANAL) [50-51]. Furthermore, while Pang2017 has been
976 predicted and reaffirmed to be attenuated, this is not the case with Pang2019.

977 Instead, SDMs have to predict that Pang2019 is non-attenuated with its N PID
978 at 48.2% [18,52,55-56]. Huo et al. [81] were able to obtain levels of viral titer
979 from Pang2019 similar to those of Wuhan-Hu-1 in VERO-E6 cells. Several
980 laboratories were also able to independently observe that Pang2019 can inflict
981 severe disease in at least one strain of mice. In contrast, virulence was not
982 observed in Pang2017 [55,74-79]. All these are again consistent with the
983 predictions of SDMs. We know that all of these SARS-CoV-2-related viruses do
984 not possess FCS, unlike SARS-CoV-2. The question then becomes the
985 following: how does Pang2019 possess similar infectivity and virulence as
986 SARS-CoV-2 without FCS when FCS-mutant non-Omicron SARS-CoV-2 is
987 largely not transmissible among ferrets?
988

989 *4.7. Measuring Virulence Using CFR, Animal Models, and Cell/Tissue Damage* 990 *Observation*

991 While Figure 1 shows a correlation between inner shell disorder and CFR, it must
992 be admitted that CFR is not necessarily the most ideal representation of virulence for at
993 least two reasons. Firstly, CFR figures are often extrapolated out of necessity [103].
994 Secondly, CFR is applied only to humans, not animals. Furthermore, virulence may
995 vary among different animals even within a single virus or variant. There are, however,
996 other methods of measuring virulence, such as animal models, viral titration, and
997 indications of cell/tissue damage after infection. We have mentioned some of the
998 animal models. It must be noted that the attenuation and aggressiveness of SARS-CoV-
999 2 variants, Pang2017-CoV and Pang2019-CoV, were reproduced by viral titrations,
1000 animal models, and inspections of cell/tissue damage after infecting cells or animals,
1001 and these experiments were conducted by at least two independent laboratories for each
1002 virus or variant [55,74-79]. The animal models included, at least, hamsters and several
1003 strains of mice. In addition, the severity of Pang2019-CoV infection was also observed
1004 in pangolins under laboratory conditions [80-82]. It can also be argued that a SARS-
1005 CoV-2-related virus may infect different types of cells in different ways, which could
1006 potentially render the interpretation of viral titration data more challenging. This is
1007 related to the argument made by some scientists that SARS-CoV-1 could infect the
1008 lower respiratory tract more efficiently in comparison to SARS-CoV-2. There are,
1009 however, hints that the arguments may not present great difficulties in the interpretation
1010 of viral titration data. Viral titrations have been created with respect to a variety of
1011 cells, including Vero E6, Calu3, and Caco2 [77]. The data show subtle but definite
1012 differences in the viral titers across three different cell lines, resulting from variations
1013 in the S-ACE-2 binding mechanism. The differences, however, are not so substantial
1014 that they would render the interpretation of viral titration data challenging, as the viral
1015 titer variations among cell types are not substantial and follow a trend. In addition, as
1016 observed later, the S of SARS-CoV-2-related viruses typically becomes more efficient
1017 in binding with the S of different cell types after several passages. With all this in
1018 mind, it is possible to present a consistent picture of virulence and infectivity. In fact, a
1019 previous study [55] was able to find a positive correlation between virulence and N
1020 PIDs based on a combination of data from viral titers, animal models, and cell plaques.
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1023 **5. The Roles of S, M, and N in Viral Replication: An Enigma**

1024 *5.1. The S Protein, Omicron, and Pangolins*

1025 We have seen that the use of S is unable to explain some crucial
1026 experimental and clinical data. This is only the tip of the iceberg, as there are
1027 more experimental and clinical data that S alone simply cannot explain or
1028 account for; moreover, thus far, attempts to do so are not reproducible or can
1029 be shown to be inherently flawed, as we have argued. There are also important
1030 biological reasons for this. For us to understand this phenomenon, we need to
1031 examine the basic fundamental biology of the virus. While S is definitely an
1032 important protein in terms of viral entry, there is no fundamental reason that S
1033 should be the most important protein in COVID-19 infectiousness and
1034 virulence, as many scientists would like to believe. Viral entry, though
1035 important, is only the first of many steps in the virus's life cycle [109]. It must
1036 be emphasized that SARS-CoV-2 encodes 19 proteins, even though not all are
1037 major proteins [109]. S is not the only major protein, and neither is it the most
1038 abundant protein. On the contrary, N and M are the most abundant major
1039 structural proteins found in the cell and virion, respectively [96-100]. For this

reason alone, we should not be surprised if N and M have greater influence on the infectivity and pathogenesis of the virus.

Further sets of perplexing evidence that contradict the “S-alone” paradigm can be found in data that pertain to pangolin-CoVs and Omicron. We need to keep in mind that all variants of SARS-CoV-2 have FCS, which is absent in all COVID-19-related bat and pangolin viruses. Many scientists thought that they had found FCS to be the true cause of COVID-19 infectiousness and virulence when, instead, it was found that SARS-CoV-2 with the FCS intact is more aggressive in respiratory cells—in contrast to the FCS-mutated one—by promoting cell-to-cell fusion. Furthermore, it has been shown that while the non-Omicron SARS-CoV-2 wild-type can be transmitted experimentally via aerosol between hamsters, no transmission was observed when the FCS-mutant was used on ferrets [113]. Again, how can this be the case, given that pangolin-CoV has no FCS and is easily transmitted between hamsters [74-75,81]?

5.2. *The S and Omicron Conundrum*

When Omicron emerged, it presented an enigma by being infectious yet attenuated. How did Omicron achieve its attenuation given that it has an FCS similarly to all other variants? Animal studies have shown that rats are unable to transmit the virus via aerosols in the laboratory. How could this be so when Omicron has been clinically shown to be highly infectious? More importantly, how can this occur when Omicron has an efficient FCS [114-115], in which its presence in other variants has been shown to induce greater transmissibility in ferrets [113]? These discrepancies point to the probability that other factors are in play. In fact, all these, as we have shown, are consistent with the workings of N and M, as summarized in Figure 5.

An attempt to navigate this “S-Omicron” paradox is the hypothesis that claims Omicron infects the cells in the upper respiratory system more easily than the lungs. Hui et al. [78] were able to isolate bronchial and lung tissues, which were infected with Omicron and previous COVID-19 variants. They were able to qualitatively observe the greater presence of viral particles and concluded that Omicron is attenuated because it replicates more easily in the lungs than in the bronchi. There are, however, several problems with this interpretation. Firstly, this observation has not, to our knowledge, been reproduced in other laboratories. In fact, several laboratories have observed efficient replications in both lungs and upper respiratory systems [77,116-117]. Furthermore, several other independent laboratories have observed that many subvariants of Omicron are even more adapted to the human ACE-2 than the non-Omicron variants [116-118]. If this is the case, why has Omicron not achieved greater virulence and infectivity similar to its predecessors?

5.3. *Evidence of the Different Roles of N and M in Experimental Data*

The story is actually even more complicated than what Hui et al. had envisaged [78]. In reality, the N and M proteins, together with knowledge of MCC, provide a more consistent and reproducible explanation for their results. In our previous publications [40,52,55], we have shown that the initial waves of Omicron had lower M PIDs than previous variants. This feature is likely a tell-tale sign of its recent interactions with a burrowing animal, possibly the pangolin. In any case, it explains why Hui et al. were able to observe more viral particles in the bronchi. It is because Omicron is more resistant to the antimicrobial mucosal enzymes that it encounters as it is being transported upwards by hair-like structures in the network of mucus-covered ciliary cells. The lungs lack ciliary cells or mucus but contain surfactants that, although antimicrobial, are less harsh than the diverse array of enzymes present. The apparent lack of viral particles is likely an indication of particles still trapped in the tissues, as there would not be MCC to bring them to the top of the lungs [88-92].

Viral titrations were also carried out using Omicron, Delta, and Wuhan-Hu-1 in lungs and bronchial tissues in the above-mentioned experiment. The data were used to support the hypothesis of the differentiated replication of Omicron in the lungs and bronchi. In one of our previous articles [55], we

1106 managed to use their data to perform multivariate analysis (Figure 6). The viral
 1107 titration data were obtained from a publicly available manuscript published by
 1108 Hui et al., while N and M PIDs—based on variants and sub-variants—were
 1109 obtained from our curated disorder database (Table 2). Regression
 1110 (multivariate) analysis was performed using the R package. The regression
 1111 analysis provides us with correlations between viral titers, and N/M PID
 1112 is measured as correlation coefficients (r) or coefficients of determination (r²). The
 1113 total n (sample size) for the entire statistical experiment, as shown in Figure 6,
 1114 is 24 (p < 0.01, n = 24, r² ~ 0.9). Statistical results were computed using the R
 1115 package, which is available publicly [119-120].

1117 We found strong correlations between N/M PIDs and viral titers. We were also
 1118 able to observe peculiar changes in the signs of the correlations when moved
 1119 from lung tissues to bronchial ones [40]. We were able to obtain a positive
 1120 correlation (r = + 0.96, Figure 6A), especially with respect to the N PID and
 1121 viral titer (VT= A * PID_N + B * Time + C, where A, B, C = coefficients and VT =
 1122 viral titer). It was, however, very startling when we received a negative
 1123 correlation (r = -0.93, Figure 6B) between PID_M/PID_N and the viral titer (VT = A
 1124 * PID_M + B * PID_N + C * Time + D, where VT = viral titer, A, B, C = coefficients,
 1125 and D = Y-intercept) [44]. What is remarkable and puzzling is the change
 1126 between the positive and negative signs. It is not only reproducing the SDMs
 1127 but also instructing us on how to use the SDMs. The change in the sign is an
 1128 indication that the greater presence of particles in the lungs is dependent on
 1129 the greater N disorder (higher PID_N), whereas the greater viral presence in the
 1130 bronchi is dependent on lower disorder in N and M PID (lower M PID and N
 1131 PID). We will also see that this change in slope (correlation) is completely
 1132 absent when viral titration is conducted in an animal model instead of tissues
 1133 (Figure 7), as viral particles can easily travel upward via MCC in the case of
 1134 animal models.

1140 **Figure 6.** Multivariate analysis of M/N disorder and viral titer [40]. **A.** Regression
 1141 analysis reveals a positive correlation between N PID and the viral titer from human
 1142 lung tissues and N PID (model: VT = A*(N PID) + B*Time + C, where VT = viral titer, A,
 1143 B = coefficients, and C = y-intercept). **B.** Regression analysis highlighted a negative
 1144 correlation between viral titers from human bronchial tissues and M/N PIDs

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(regression model: $VT = A*(M\text{ PID}) + B(N\text{PID}) + C*Time + D$, where $VT =$ viral titer, A , B , $C =$ coefficients, and $D =$ y-intercept). The analysis is a statistical extension of the experiment of Hui et al. [40,43]. Data pertaining to viral titrations and PIDs are from the experiment of Hui et al. and available in Table 2 (which can also be found in previous publications).

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Prior to this investigation, we focused on the hard outer shell (low M PID) with respect to its resistance to the onslaught of mucosal antimicrobial enzymes and on greater N disorder with respect to its ability to assist in providing more efficient viral replication [18-20], but the experiment also showed us that N plays a role in protecting the virion from damage [52,55]. This is something we had overlooked, even though evidence from the very beginning indicated that harder inner shells protect viruses such as NiV, EIAV, DENV, and rabies [34-35,55-56,65-67].

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We conducted a similar regression study, as observed in Figure 7, using the experimental data of Guo et al. [75]. Again, we were able to obtain titration data from the published study of Guo et al. with the respective N and M PIDs, which depend on the SARS-CoV-2 variant and pangolin-CoV isolate, obtained from our curated database. As with the data from Hui et al., we carried out regression analysis to obtain the correlation coefficients (r) and coefficients of determination (r^2), which were grouped according to the samples' location in the respiratory system (Figure 7, total $n = 30$, $p < 0.01$, $r^2 \sim 0.9$).

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Guo et al. used Pang2017 and hamsters instead of Omicron and tissue cultures, respectively [65]. Therefore, M becomes an unreliable independent variable as there is hardly any difference between the M PID of Pang2017 and non-Omicron SARS-CoV-2. We also expected to observe the full effect of MCC since Guo et al. [75] used an animal model, in contrast to the use of tissues by Hui et al. [78], i.e., the viral particles are more able to move freely between different parts of the respiratory system via MCC. Positive correlations between N PID and viral titer were observed in samples collected from all three areas of the respiratory system, as observed in Figure 7, which helps validate SDMs and the results described in the previous sections.

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Figure 7. Multivariate analysis of N/M disorder (PID) and viral titer of pangolin-CoV/SARS-CoV-2 in VERO-E6 (regression: $VT = A * (N \text{ PID}) + B * \text{Time} + C$, where VT = viral titer, A, B = coefficients, and C = intercept) [40]. The results are a statistical extension of the experiment of Guo et al. [40,75]. Viral titration data are from the experiment of Guo et al., whereas PID data are available in Table 2 and previous publications.

5.4. Hui et al. Experiment: S-Alone Hypothesis vs. SDMs

The S-alone hypothesis argues that SARS-CoV-1 infects the lower respiratory tract more easily as its S binds more efficiently to the cells in the lower respiratory system. The same argument has been made to account for the lower virulence of Omicron compared to other variants. Hui et al. tried to show this phenomenon. They cultured various variants in bronchial and lung tissues. Their viral titration data show lower viral titers for Omicron in the lungs than in the bronchial tissues. When we applied their viral titration data to carry out more elaborate statistical analysis correlating viral titers with N and M PIDs, our results, however, revealed a different pattern [40]. There are strong correlations between viral titers and N/M PIDs in both bronchial and lung tissues. Moreover, positive and negative correlations were found in the lung and tissues, respectively. The results not only reproduce the predictions of SDMs but also provide insight into how SDMs should be interpreted. The positive correlation between N PIDs and viral titers in the lungs reveals that the greater presence of viral particles is due to the greater N disorder (PID), which depends on the variant—keeping in mind that the lungs have surfactants in lieu of mucus. Surfactants exert some antimicrobial effects, but these are far less potent than the diverse array of antimicrobial enzymes present in mucus. This is the reason why there is a strong positive correlation between viral titers in the lung tissues and N PID and a weaker correlation with M PID. The puzzling question is then the following: Why is there a negative correlation between viral titers in bronchial tissues and N/M PIDs? The answer is related to the fact that, in contrast to the lungs, bronchial tissues, similarly to most upper respiratory tissues, have mucus. A negatively correlated M PID means that the hard M is protecting the virus from antimicrobial damage. What we did not expect was a correlation with N disorder. At that point, we realized that this result indicates that N also plays a role in protecting the virion from damage, especially when exposed to an onslaught of antimicrobial enzymes. The results reveal how predictions can be interpreted using SDMs. Indeed, we had previously observed that some viruses, such as the rabies virus (RABV), with harder inner and outer shells thrive better in harsh environments, such as exposure to saliva [65-67]. It must also be noted that M and N bind to each other in close proximity in the virion. Further literature searches have provided experimental evidence that M and N, taken together, permit greater structural integrity via the non-covalent binding between them. This provides support for computational results that suggest that both M and N protect the virion from damage.

Our more elaborate statistical analysis indicates that the higher viral titer of Omicron is not due to an increased number of viral particles in the bronchial tissues, nor due to differences in the S protein. Rather, it arises from the virus's enhanced ability to resist damage from the abundant mucosal antimicrobial enzymes present in the bronchial tissues. Omicron's greater resistance to antimicrobial enzymes arises from its greater hardness in both M and N (N PID: 44.8%; M PID: 5.4%). The particular Omicron variant used was BA1, which was the original subvariant that was first detected in South Africa. While all Omicron variants have lower N PIDs, BA1 has the peculiar characteristic of an even lower M PID (~5.4%) than all other variants or Omicron subvariants (~5.9%) [55]. As a result of this phenomenon and its harder N, it can resist antimicrobial enzymes in the bronchial tissues; thus, there is a greater presence of viral particles. In the lung tissues, however, there is a lesser presence of antimicrobial enzymes; however, because Omicron's N PID is substantially lower, it is unable to replicate as fast as the other variants, especially in the lungs. This phenomenon is detected by the more elaborate statistics applied, and this result is arguably more plausible than the one presented by Hui et al. [78], as the former shows a more intricate reason for the results of the latter.

5.5. The Role of MCC in Virulence and Infectivity

Puzzling and seemingly contradictory results are observed in the viral titration of pangolins, as seen in Figure 7 (Guo et al. [75]). Unlike the statistical findings from Hui et al.'s data, the statistical analysis using the data from Guo et al. [75] shows positive correlations for viral titers with respect to N PIDs in both the upper and lower respiratory tracts. While this may appear to contradict the results we just discussed, it is not actually inconsistent. The experiment conducted by Guo et al. was based on live hamsters infected with pangolin-CoV. They measured the viral titers by extracting samples from euthanized hamsters. Hui et al., on the other hand, relied solely on viruses grown in bronchial and lung tissues. Therefore, we should expect the full effects of MCC in the experiment of Guo et al., but only limited MCC effects are observed in the experiment of Hui et al. because the viral particles produced across the respiratory system—including the lower respiratory system—will move upward towards the nasal region for expulsion. This is what the statistical results shown in Figure 7, unlike those in Figure 6, are revealing. The results of Figures 6-7 cast doubt on the hypothesis that SARS-CoV-1 is less infectious but more virulent due to its S protein binding more efficiently to ACE-2 cells in the lower respiratory tract. This is because MCC transports much of the viral particles produced in the lower respiratory tract upward to the nasal region for expulsion from the body. The same argument has been made for the more virulent SARS-CoV-2 variants. It seems that a more plausible scenario is that the virus replicates approximately the same amount throughout the respiratory system. The more virulent strain or variant with higher N PID replicates extensively throughout the respiratory system, particularly in the lungs. However, the extent to which viral particles are expelled from the body depends on the virus's ability to withstand the onslaught of mucosal and salivary antimicrobial enzymes via a harder M.

5.6. SDMs Account for MCC in Virulence and Infectivity

One problem with the “S-Alone” hypothesis involving SARS-CoV-1/2 virulence and infectivity is that it is oblivious to current physiological knowledge, namely, MCC. Even if SARS-CoV-1 does bind more efficiently to the lower respiratory tract compared to the upper respiratory tract, thereby rendering SARS-CoV-1 less infectious but more virulent, MCC entails that the viral particles will move upward towards the nasal region to be expelled. This, of course, assumes that the viral particles will survive the onslaught of antimicrobial enzymes during transportation by mucus-covered ciliary cells. The MCC factor must be considered if we attempt to demonstrate the difference in virulence and infectivity between Omicron and non-Omicron variants. Because MCC is an important principle in physiology, MCC must therefore be essential in explaining the mechanisms of virulence and infectivity manifestations. SDMs, unlike the S-alone hypothesis, can account for MCC, and MCC can explain the link between infectivity and virulence via SDMs. MCC and SDMs, therefore, complement each other in accounting for differences in the infectivity and virulence manifestations of SARS-CoV-1/2 and SARS-CoV-2 variants.

5.7. The HCoV-NL63 Enigma

The above sections do not imply that S plays no role in infectivity and virulence; rather, they indicate that S does not contribute to infectivity and virulence in many of the ways commonly assumed. Its roles should be evaluated in the broader context, alongside other proteins such as N and M. To understand it further, we turn our attention to another human CoV. The only other known human CoV (HCoV)—other than SARS-CoV-1/2—that binds to ACE-2 is NL63 [121-126]. HCoV-NL30 usually manifests itself as a mild cold even though it is known to be capable of infecting both the lower and upper respiratory tracts. NL63 and SARS-CoV-1/2 are not closely related, as they comprise alphacoronavirus and betacoronavirus, respectively [126]. It can be argued that NL63 is somewhat less infectious than SARS-CoV-2 since the former usually only infects children and immunocompromised individuals, such as the elderly, unlike the latter.

NL63 has no FCS recognition site even if an FCS sequence has been detected at S2 [123-124]. While cleavage is seen at the Golgi apparatus of cells infected by SARS-CoV-2, it is not observed in NL63 infection. Keeping in mind that SARS-CoV-1 does not have FCS, unlike SARS-CoV-2 [101-103], the absence of an FCS recognition site presents an intriguing enigma. If NL63 and SARS-CoV1 have no FCS recognition site, why is NL63 obviously less infectious than SARS-CoV-1? Conversely, if SARS-CoV-

2 has an FCS recognition site, unlike NL63 and SARS-CoV-1, why does SARS-CoV-2 exhibit infectivity that is comparable to NL63 when compared to SARS-CoV-1, given the fact that both COVID-19 and NL63, but not SARS-CoV-1, are endemic? We know that SARS-CoV-1 has limited infectivity as there were only 8,422 known cases of infection, and it is now extinct, whereas COVID-19 and NL63 are endemic even to this day [3,12126]. All these phenomena seem to contradict the idea that the presence of FCS is responsible for higher infectivity [102-103]. As for pathogenesis, why are SARS-CoV-2 and NL63 substantially less virulent than SARS-CoV-1 when SARS-CoV-2 is the only virus of the three that has an FCS recognition site given that the presence of FCS is associated with greater pathogenesis?

Likewise, the relationship between S-ACE-2 affinity and pathogenesis or infectivity can cause substantial confusion, especially when NL63 is taken into consideration. We have observed that the affinity of SARS-CoV-2 S with respect to human ACE-2 is much higher than that of SARS-CoV-1. Many scientists have postulated that this discrepancy is responsible for SARS-CoV-2's higher infectivity, especially among humans [9-11]. This postulation is, however, unreproducible, as it has been shown that NL63 S's affinity for ACE-2 is less than that of SARS-CoV-1 [126]. How could this be possible when NL63 is obviously substantially more infectious than SARS-CoV-1 for the reasons already mentioned? All these questions form a conundrum that is difficult to explain by S alone and is more effectively explained when the different roles of S, N, and M are taken into consideration.

This virus is, however, also enigmatic for SDMs, as its N disorder is very close to that of SARS-CoV-1 (N PIDs: 49.8% vs. 50.2%), but NL63 is, of course, not as virulent. Does this mean that SDMs are wrong? If we look closely, we will find that this is not necessarily true. SDMs usually function better when the compared viruses are closely related. NL63 is not closely related to SARS-CoV-1/2; as a result, the proteins, in general, are not similar between the two. Because of the differences in proteins, especially those beyond shell proteins, other factors can come into play, such as differences in the toxicities of other proteins. This is a limitation of SDMs.

Nevertheless, in this case, comparisons using SDMs are possible in this case. While the NL63 N PID is higher than SARS-CoV-2 but comparable to SARS-CoV-1, the M disorder tells a different story. It is substantially higher than that of SARS-CoV-1/2 (NL63 M PID: ~11%; SARS-CoV-2 M PID: 5.8-54.%; SARS-CoV-1 M PID: ~9%). Applying current knowledge from SDMs, the relatively soft NL63 M and N proteins imply that, although a comparatively large number of viral particles may be produced even in the lower respiratory tract, these particles are easily damaged by mucosal antimicrobial enzymes as soon as they are produced. It is for this reason that NL63 is usually not dangerous. If we scrutinize the clinical data more carefully, however, we observe that NL63 is capable of infecting both the upper and lower respiratory tracts [121-122] and that the individuals it infects in this manner are mainly children and immunocompromised adults, such as the elderly. These clinical manifestations may be the result of its ability to replicate in larger quantities in all areas of the respiratory system if unchecked by the immune system, including the antimicrobial enzymes in the mucus. SDMs also suggest that, despite its greater vulnerability to damage by mucosal antimicrobial enzymes, some particles can reach the nasal region to be shed because greater quantities are produced as a result of a more disordered N. The fact that children and immunocompromised adults are more easily infected could provide further support to the idea that only limited quantities of viral particles are shed. Children often play in close contact with each other, especially at preschools.

5.8. *The Protective Roles of Outer and Inner Shells*

We have observed how both the outer (M) and inner (N) shells play roles in protecting SARS-CoV-2 from antimicrobial enzymes in the mucus and saliva. Apparently, this is not the only virus to exhibit such properties. There are several

1380 studies that report that viruses exposed to saliva usually have hard outer shells and
1381 often also have hard inner shells. Examples of such viruses are the EIAV, rabies virus,
1382 and Zika virus [4,34-35,66-67]. EIAV is transmitted between horses via horseflies that
1383 suck the blood of an infected horse, storing it in their mouthpiece with their saliva
1384 before sucking the blood of a new host, which is thereby infected. The rabies virus
1385 resides near the salivary gland of the host and is therefore exposed to saliva. Similarly,
1386 ZIKV is exposed to saliva when it is retained in the mouth of an Aedes mosquito
1387 during feeding on the blood of an infected host. These phenomena, however, do not
1388 necessarily indicate that all viruses have a degree of inner shell hardness, as all viruses
1389 exposed to saliva usually have hard outer shells. This is the case in the flavivirus
1390 family, in which the viruses are usually insect-borne and have a hard outer M, but a
1391 few viruses, such as ZIKV, also have a harder capsid.

1392 5.9. *The Functions of M and N*

1393 A great way to gain more insights into the structure, nature, and functions of viral
1394 proteins, such as N and M, is by inspecting SARS-CoV-2 using microscopy,
1395 particularly electron microscopy (EM) [127-128,148-149]. Observations of the SARS-
1396 CoV-2 virion, including M and N, did not reveal anything unusual that is not seen in
1397 other CoVs. M spans the viral membrane, which is a lipid bilayer of about 5nm, with
1398 the former protruding approximately 2.5 nm, which is not unusual for CoVs [127-128,
1399 147-148]. Inspections of the SARS-CoV-2 using powerful EM have revealed the
1400 reasons that M and N are the most abundant proteins in the virion and cell,
1401 respectively. M spans the entire membrane, which encloses the entire virion, whereas N
1402 encases the RNA genome [127-128]. The structural arrangement itself suggests
1403 protective roles of the two proteins. M binds strongly to both S and N. The affinities for
1404 S and N allow M and N to play important roles in the assembly and budding of viral
1405 particles [107]. Because of the strong affinity between M and N, the greater flexibility
1406 in N provides for more efficient recognition between N and M [16,30-32]. This is one
1407 of the reasons that greater N disorder allows faster and more effective viral replication.
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1410 There is yet another property of M and N that has been observed using EM. This
1411 involves the nature of M and N binding. Powerful EM techniques were used to observe
1412 that the C-terminus of M binds to N via an ionic interaction [129]; moreover, in the
1413 absence of this interaction, the entire virion collapses under harsh conditions, such as
1414 high salt or PH levels. This important observation provides support to the suggestion
1415 that M and N play roles in protecting the virion. While M protects the entire virion, N
1416 is likely to specifically protect the genomic RNA, as N encases the RNA; thus, strong
1417 affinities between the two entities exist [106-109]. N's affinity to the viral RNA has
1418 provided N with many important roles, especially those pertaining to viral replication.
1419 This includes assembly and RNA transcription [107-109,129-131]. Because of its
1420 important roles in replication and the life cycle of the virus, we can observe how N
1421 disorder can easily affect virulence and infectivity along with M disorder, as greater N
1422 disorder promotes more efficient protein-protein/RNA/lipid/carbohydrate recognition
1423 [16,30-33,68].
1424

1425 We have attempted to show that SDMs are highly reproducible and can account
1426 for many of the properties and manifestations of SARS-CoV-2-related viruses and
1427 COVID-19. Such reproducibilities should not be surprising, as M and N are the most
1428 abundant proteins in the virion and cell, respectively, and they play major roles in the
1429 life cycle of the virus, especially regarding its replication [106-109]. Nevertheless, we
1430 need to keep in mind that M and N are, of course, not the only viral proteins in CoVs.
1431 While they play major roles in the replication of the virus, other proteins also play
1432 roles. For instance, N binds to NSP2 before the transcription of viral RNA takes place
1433 [129]. Since it involves other proteins, we should therefore expect limitations and
1434 potentials in N and M, similarly to what we have observed in S. One such example is
1435 the use of virulence-inner SDM to compare distant viruses within a family. This is the
1436 case when the virus's proteins are essentially very different in sequence and use
1437 different receptors. Other examples of the limitations of SDMs can be detected in the
1438 results of certain animal and viral titration studies. A discussion with further details can
1439 be provided in the next subsection.
1440
1441
1442

1443
1444 5.10. *A More Accurate Understanding of S Comes with the Study of Other Proteins*

1445 The above sections do not show that S does not play any role in infectivity
1446 and virulence; rather, they show that S does not play a role in infectivity and
1447 virulence in the manner that many scientists have envisaged. To be able to gain
1448 a more accurate understanding of the real role of S, a better understanding of
1449 the role of other viral proteins, especially the more abundant major proteins, is
1450 necessary.

1451 We have presented evidence to show that S is not able to account for the
1452 differences in virulence and infectivity between SARS-CoV-1 and SARS-CoV-2.
1453 We have also seen that the viral titers of the two viruses are different, with
1454 higher titers, implying higher virulence in the case of SARS-CoV-1. While the
1455 presence and absence of FCS in SARS-CoV-2 and SARS-CoV-1, respectively,
1456 could explain the greater virulence of SARS-CoV-1, it does not explain the
1457 greater virulence of SARS-CoV-2. The SDMs using N and M provide a
1458 comprehensive and coherent explanation that is more reproducible. The SDMs
1459 are also able to explain the differences among COVID-19 viruses, even if they
1460 are more complex. Much of the problem lies in the fact that many of the viruses
1461 have yet to be observed to spread to the human population, and their actual
1462 pathogenicity and infectivity among humans cannot be accurately determined.
1463 For these phenomena, we must rely on animal models, the use of which is
1464 tricky and requires extrapolation. Incorrect inferences based on incorrect
1465 extrapolations and assumptions can easily be made, as we have observed in the
1466 disastrous pre-clinical studies of thalidomide using mice, rats, and rabbits
1467 [133].
1468

1469
1470 In the case of COVID-19, it was believed that the FCS is responsible for
1471 infectiousness and virulence based on an animal model, in which infected and
1472 uninfected ferrets were caged together. One group had a few ferrets infected
1473 with wild-type SARS-CoV-2 (WT), whereas the other ferrets were infected with
1474 a mutated strain without FCS. The result was that the WT did infect some of
1475 the uninfected ferrets, whereas those infected with the FCS-mutant did not
1476 infect others [112]. Based on this experiment, it is easy to conclude that FCS is
1477 responsible for high transmissibility. A picture that contradicts this conclusion
1478 was obtained when similar experiments were performed using pangolin-CoVs
1479 and Omicron.
1480

1481 In various independent laboratories, uninfected Syrian hamsters were
1482 easily infected by those infected with pangolin-CoVs (Pang2017 and Pang2019)
1483 when caged together by contact, although this did not occur as easily as via
1484 aerosol [75-76,81]. Similar experiments using Omicron yielded comparable
1485 results [76-77,114-115]. Furthermore, it was observed that Wuhan-Hu-1 is more
1486 easily spread via aerosol, whereas pangolin-CoVs and, to some extent,
1487 Omicron were not as easily transmitted, even though the latter have been
1488 shown to spread easily clinically. Keeping in mind that pangolin-CoVs do not
1489 have FCS but Omicron does, these experiments highlight that the issue is more
1490 complex than it seems, and it is easy to come to the wrong conclusion without
1491 a more complete picture. Adding to the confusion, why does Pang2019 exhibit
1492 more virulence than Wuhan-Hu-1, which is not observed in Pang2017 and
1493 Omicron?
1494

1495 A more complete and reproducible answer can be found if the analysis
1496 takes the various roles of N, M, and S into consideration. It is obvious that S
1497 plays some role in the infectivity of the virus, but it is a mistake to assume that
1498 this role is as overreaching as suggested by some. SDMs explain that all thus
1499 far known variants are highly infectious, as COVID-19 patients shed large
1500 quantities of the virus because its hard outer shell M helps prevent virion
1501 disintegration caused by salivary and mucosal enzymes before being expelled
1502 by the body. While the abnormally hard M ensures a certain high level of
1503 spread, higher N PID (i.e., higher levels of N disorder) results in greater levels
1504 of viral replication and viral load (the mechanism has been explained in
1505 Section 5.9), especially in vital organs such as the lungs, which could increase
1506 the virulence of the virus and the amount of viral particles expunged from the
1507 body, even if the quantity of viral shedding is already high. This is exactly the
1508 case with Wuhan-Hu-1 and Omicron. Omicron has a relatively low N disorder

(PID ~43%) and is therefore milder than the other variants, but it is also infectious, as it also exhibits low M PIDs (~5.4-5.9). Wuhan-Hu-1, on the other hand, is both highly infectious and more virulent, as its M and N PIDs are low and relatively high, respectively. The aforementioned animal model suggests that Wuhan-Hu-1 is relatively more infectious than Omicron. Since both SDMs and clinical studies suggest high infectiousness in the two viruses, the experiment can only be consistent with SDMs and clinical studies if the infectiousness of the two viruses is only relative in differences [71-73,114-115]. We have to be careful when using animal models since extrapolation is necessary when we attempt to link the results to human infections [132].

Furthermore, human infectivity tells only part of the story in the evolution of SARS-CoV-2 and its ancestral strain. We must also keep in mind the infectivity of SARS-CoV-2 and its relatives in different animal hosts. Furthermore, we must pay attention to data pertaining to virulence, including viral titration and cell damage. As virulence can be linked to infectivity using the SDMs and MCC, as shown in Section 5.4-5.6, these factors are important when it comes to the interpretation of the results of animal models involving infectivity. We will also observe, in the next section, that the best understanding of the results comes from our knowledge of S, N, and M.

5.11. Biological Implications of a More Rigid M

We have seen in Figure 2 that all SARS-CoV-2-related viruses have an extraordinarily hard outer M. Nearly all CoVs have PIDs of above 8. The exceptions are CoVs associated with burrowing animals. CoVs closely related to SARS-CoV-2 have M PIDs between 4% and 6.3% (Table 2). The differences between burrowing and non-burrowing seem small, even if statistically significant. A clearer understanding is obtained, however, if we consider the functions and virion physiology related to M. M is the most abundant viral protein that spans the entire virion. Therefore, even with a few mutations that lower the disorder of M, the rigidity of the SARS-CoV-2 membrane is likely be strengthened substantially by the sheer abundance of M. This is especially true when the virus is in its native state and when M plays the essential role of protecting the virion from external attacks.

A question that arises is as follows: If SARS-CoV-2 M is more rigid, how is it able to perform its other functions that require conformational changes, such as viral entry and protein assembly? If we look at Table 2, we observe that the minimum M PID seen in all CoVs is around 4%. Obviously, this is the minimum level of disorder that is needed for M to have sufficient flexibility in order to perform its other roles that require conformational change. An M PID of 0% theoretically means that the protein has no room for conformation changes. Therefore, an M PID of 0 % means that the virus is not functional. The data in Table 2 and Figure 2 seem to reinforce this idea due to the existence of the 4% minimum cutoff point. While a lower M PID offers greater protection to the virus in its native state, it could also imply that M could have less efficiency in undergoing conformational changes. We do not, however, know how substantial this impact is on the efficiency of conformational changes that are necessary for processes such as viral entry and protein assembly. Extrapolating from the efficiency of SARS-CoV-2 (M PID ~ 6.3%) with respect to replication, it is likely not substantial; however, once again, this is only an extrapolation that must be confirmed by experimental results.

6. Potentials and Limitations of M and N in SDMs

6.1. A Comparative Analysis of SARS-CoV-2, Pangolin-CoVs, and Laotian Bat-CoV Experiments Using S, N, and M

A more comprehensive analysis can be accomplished when examining M, N, and S in the experimental data for SARS-CoV-2, bat-CoVs, and pangolin-CoVs. We have observed that all COVID-19-related viruses are potentially infectious because of their abnormally hard M. We have also observed that Pang2019, BANAL (Laotian bat-CoV), and Wuhan-Hu-1 are all potentially virulent because of their high N PIDs (~48%), whereas Pang2017 and Omicron

1571 are attenuated as a result of their relatively low N PIDs (~44%). These have
1572 been largely reproduced. Cells infected with Pang2017 or Omicron have signs
1573 of lower viral growth and cytopathic effects [55,74]. Similarly, animal models
1574 have exhibited less severity. In contrast, however, viral titers of cells infected
1575 by Pang2019 [80-82] and Wuhan-Hu-1 [75,79] are higher than those infected by
1576 Pang2017 or Omicron [55,74-76], just as predicted by the SDMs. In contrast,
1577 mice were observed to be severely sickened by Pang2019 [81-82]. We need to
1578 keep in mind that this trend is true even though FCS is found only in SARS-
1579 CoV-2, including Omicron. Therefore, the stark differences in the results of
1580 various experiments can only be accounted for when the roles of N and M are
1581 considered.
1582

1583 6.2. Evidence of the Potentials and Limitations of S: Viral Entry and Replication 1584

1585
1586
1587 The data for the Laotian bat-CoVs present an enigma [50-51]. It was
1588 shown that BANAL S binds to ACE2 in a different manner from SARS-CoV-2,
1589 even as the BANAL viruses bind efficiently to human cells. Ironically, even
1590 though the N PID of BANAL is similar to those of Wuhan-Hu-1 and Pang2019,
1591 no severe disease was detected in mice infected by BANAL-236. This seemed to
1592 be inconsistent with what SDMs predicted until the data were studied very
1593 carefully. If we inspect the viral titration data, we can observe that the viral
1594 titers in VERO-E6 cells are high and comparable to Wuhan-Hu-1, but this is not
1595 the case in CALU-3 cells, where the difference is larger; it should also be kept
1596 in mind that a VERO-E6 cell is of kidney origin, whereas CALU cells are
1597 respiratory. This implies that BANAL-236 is more adapted to kidney cells than
1598 respiratory ones, presumably because of its S structure. We also need to keep in
1599 mind that the Laotian bat-CoV S protein binds to ACE-2 in a different manner
1600 [51].

1601 While this serves as evidence that S does play a role in infectivity, it does
1602 not show that SDM results are wrong or not reproducible. Instead, this
1603 phenomenon points to the correct manner by which SDMs should be
1604 interpreted. Firstly, the experimental data remind us that SDMs predict
1605 *potential* virulence—not necessarily actual virulence—and this potential
1606 virulence arises from the high viral load in at least one organ, which is
1607 populated with cells that the virus can enter more easily. A second lesson to be
1608 learned from the data is that SDMs predict virulence in general—not just
1609 humans—since N PID correlates best with the highest viral titers among
1610 various cell types [55,74-79], and high viral loads are associated with organ
1611 failures. While human COVID-19 fatality is mainly associated with pulmonary
1612 (lung) failures, this may not be necessarily so for other animals. Therefore,
1613 SDMs are predicting potential virulence in general—not only in humans.
1614

1615
1616 If there is evidence that S does play some role in infectivity and virulence
1617 via viral loads, the question then becomes the following: How easily does S
1618 adapt to bind more efficiently? It would seem that greater S fitness may be
1619 more easily acquired than many believe. Experiments have shown that
1620 COVID-19 viruses acquire a greater ability to infect the lungs after passing to
1621 humanized mice several times [133-136]. Furthermore, a closer comparison of
1622 the two may provide clues. Given the fact that both BANAL-236 and Pang2019
1623 have high N PIDs, why has Pang2019 been shown to be virulent to humanized
1624 mice, unlike BANAL-236? Evidently, Pang2019 S is more adapted than
1625 BANAL-236. To understand why this is the case, we need to look at the
1626 evolutionary differences between the two viruses. If we look at Figure 5B,
1627 which shows a phylogenetic tree using M, we observe that Pang2019 is more
1628 closely related to SARS-CoV-2 than BANAL-236. This implies that Pang2019
1629 was exposed to a similar range of hosts as Wuhan-Hu-1. What is also
1630 remarkable is that both BANAL-236 and Pangolin-CoVs, unlike SARS-CoV-2,
1631 do not have FCS. It is likely that Pang2019 split off from SARS-CoV-2 to mainly
1632 infect pangolins, and as a result, it lost its FCS while still maintaining much of
1633 its S structure. This may also have implications for Peacock et al.'s FCS-mutant
1634 experiment [113]. It is possible that the FCS-deficient S compensates for its
1635 deficit by binding to ACE-2 in a different manner over a longer period, as is the

1636 case with Pang2019. Moreover, as we will observe, it is easy for S to quickly
1637 adapt to the ACE-2 of a particular species or cell type in a laboratory.
1638

1639 It is evident that S must be at least sufficiently adapted to ACE-2 in order
1640 to even be infectious, but in order for SARS-CoV-2 to have any sustained
1641 infectivity or virulence, other factors must also come into play, especially the
1642 roles of M and N, as observed in the experimental and clinical evidence
1643 pertaining to SARS-CoV-1/2. The question then becomes the following: How
1644 difficult is it for S to gain sufficient adaptation to respiratory cells? The earlier
1645 section argues that it may not be very difficult. Several studies have shown that
1646 COVID-19 viruses can easily and quickly adapt to human respiratory cells in
1647 the laboratory [133-136]. Acquiring abnormally hard M that provides for
1648 potentially high infectivity, on the other hand, may not be as easy. It is
1649 relatively easy to identify CoVs that efficiently bind to the S protein of
1650 respiratory cells [101,109,118], possess an FCS [101,109,118], or exhibit easily
1651 adaptable S [108,131-132]. In contrast, CoVs with an abnormally hard M are
1652 rare, as most CoVs are not intimately associated with a burrowing animal,
1653 unlike COVID-19-related viruses [4,16-20,53-56].
1654

1655 *6.3. Greater Model Reproducibility and Reliability Come When More Proteins are* 1656 *Considered*

1657
1658
1659 The greater reliability and reproducibility of SDMs arise from the fact that
1660 they consider the disorder of two major proteins, M and N, which are most
1661 abundant in the virion and infected cell, respectively. In fact, SDMs become
1662 unreliable if M or N is omitted from consideration. SDMs are reliable and
1663 reproducible in most cases, except on certain occasions when the role of S must
1664 be taken into serious consideration, as observed in the case of the Laotian bat-
1665 CoVs. For this reason, we cannot dismiss S or any other proteins as
1666 unimportant. In fact, as we have shown, SDMs become even more reliable and
1667 reproducible when S (or other protein) is taken into consideration. This trend is
1668 consistent with what we know about the biology of viral replication. Viral
1669 replication involves multiple proteins, even if there are proteins that play more
1670 major roles than others.
1671

1672 *6.4. Limitations and Potentials of N, M, and SDMs*

1673 We have already touched on the limitation of SDMs. We have seen that it
1674 cannot account for some experimental results conducted using BANAL
1675 (Laotian bat-CoVs). They are, for example, unable to account for the differences
1676 in the viral titrations of BANAL-236 and SARS-CoV-2 with respect to different
1677 cell types (e.g., CALU, COCA, Vero-E6) [51-52,77]. The significance of the
1678 differences, however, needs further investigation, as other researchers have
1679 shown that SARS-CoV-2 becomes more efficient in replication as several
1680 passages are made in each cell type. Nevertheless, this points to the role of S,
1681 which is a limitation of SDMs. Currently, SDMs are involved in viral shell
1682 proteins, which, in the case of CoVs, are the N and M proteins. Given that
1683 SARS-CoV-2 has 29 viral proteins and many are also involved in the replication
1684 process [106-109], there will be limitations if only one or two proteins are used
1685 to study infectivity, virulence, or long COVID. This is, of course, the case in
1686 SDMs, which currently use only M and N. In fact, as already mentioned,
1687 without either M or N, SDMs would be of limited reproducibility and
1688 reliability, and they would have much difficulty explaining the underlying
1689 cause of infectivity and virulence.
1690

1691 Ironically, the question is then the following: How can M and N account for
1692 infectivity and virulence with even a decent level of reproducibility and
1693 reliability when the limitation of using only two proteins is considered? The
1694 answer could lie in two factors. The important roles of M and N, as observed
1695 above, are likely to be partly responsible. Secondly, a hint of the overwhelming
1696 importance of M and N can be observed via the massive abundance of
1697 proteins, which is not seen in other COVID-19 viral proteins. This could also
1698 reinforce the idea that the two proteins play greater major roles in the
1699 functioning of the virus. While the focus of this review is on SDMs and N and
1700 M proteins, we do not dismiss the importance of S or any other viral proteins.
1701 This review, however, attempts to underscore the importance of M and N in

1702 infectivity and virulence, as exemplified by the examples shown in Figures 6-7.
1703 The results in Figures 6-7 do not invalidate the role of S—as Hui et al.
1704 attempted to demonstrate—but suggest that the currently understudied roles
1705 of M and N could even overshadow that of S with respect to infectivity,
1706 virulence, and potentially long COVID. Of course, SDMs would become more
1707 reproducible and reliable if more viral proteins, such as S and NSP7, are
1708 considered in the models. However, currently, SDMs have not reached the
1709 stage where the roles of other proteins can be incorporated.
1710
1711
1712
1713

1714 **7. SDMs Hint at a Novel Immune Evasion Strategy Used by SARS-CoV-2 in** 1715 **Long COVID**

1716 1717 *7.1. The Long COVID Enigma and Pangolin Footprints*

1718 One unusual characteristic that is often found among some COVID-19
1719 patients is long COVID, which is when symptoms persist for weeks, months, or
1720 even years after the initial infection [57-58,110-111]. While the cause of long
1721 COVID remains largely a mystery, SDMs offer the most logical and plausible
1722 explanation yet. We have seen that all COVID-19-related viruses have
1723 extraordinarily hard outer shells (M) that are not found in any CoVs, except
1724 those associated with burrowing animals. We have also observed how SDMs
1725 explain that the hard M allows for greater COVID-19 infectiousness by
1726 providing more resistance to mucosal and salivary antimicrobial enzymes,
1727 often without the greater virulence that is associated with greater N disorder
1728 [18-20,52,55-56]. Similarly to how a hard M provides resistance to antimicrobial
1729 enzymes, it will almost certainly also provide resistance to other destructive
1730 mechanisms offered by other aspects of the host immune system. This is
1731 possible as clinical studies have shown that large amounts of the virus tend to
1732 remain in the body even after months [110-111]. We will further explore this
1733 link via a further examination of the various known aspects of immunology
1734 related to this matter, as detailed in the following subsections.
1735
1736
1737

1738 *7.2. Hard M Resistance to Virolysis by Phagocytes and a Complement System*

1739
1740 In order to further examine the role of an abnormally hard M in long
1741 COVID, we need to look more closely at how the immune system eliminates
1742 invading foreign particles, especially viruses. Our knowledge of immunology
1743 helps focus our attention on proteins produced by the complement system and
1744 lysosome [135-142]. These enzymes are experimentally shown to damage
1745 viruses and viral membranes.

1746 Complement proteins are mainly produced by hepatocytes in the liver,
1747 even though they are secreted by monocytes, macrophages, and epithelial cells
1748 in the intestines. There are at least 30 types of complement proteins [139]. B and
1749 T cells, along with antibodies, can alert the complement system in the presence
1750 of foreign matter such as bacteria or virus. Complementary proteins assemble
1751 and bind to a protein at the targeted membrane, and the protein complex
1752 punches holes in the membrane. Apoptosis occurs in the case of bacteria or
1753 infected cells, whereas, in the case of a virus, this is referred to as virolysis. It is
1754 at this point in COVID-19 and long COVID that the hard M may make it
1755 difficult for the complement system to carry out its function, as the proteins are
1756 likely unable to penetrate the membrane since M spans the entire membrane
1757 that covers the virion.
1758
1759

1760 *7.3. Resistance to Virolysis Within a Phagocyte May Provide the Virus a Place to* 1761 *Dwell: Possible Reservoir*

1762
1763 A second way that the immune system attempts to eliminate pathogens is
1764 to expose them to digestive enzymes [130-131,140]. Phagocytes, such as

1765 macrophages, will first engulf the microbe or microbial protein, and upon
1766 phagocytosis, the immune system will attempt to digest the particle via
1767 lysosomes [138-141]. The problem with this strategy, however, is that many
1768 pathogens are somehow resistant to the exposure of digestive enzymes and
1769 end up residing in the phagocytes [140-141]. An ongoing enigma pertaining to
1770 long COVID concerns the existence and location of a viral reservoir that
1771 persists long after the initial infection. A hard outer shell could prevent
1772 phagocytes from destroying the virus, allowing it to survive within these
1773 immune cells. The observation of an abnormally hard M, along with our
1774 knowledge of immunology, suggests that the first place to look at is none other
1775 than the phagocyte and, in particular, macrophage itself, and current research
1776 supports this. Huot et al. [144] found the presence of SARS-CoV-2 in the lungs
1777 of patients with symptoms of long COVID, whereas several other research
1778 groups have found its presence in organs and tissues throughout the body
1779 [110-111], which is consistent with the fact that phagocytes can be found in
1780 nearly all organs in the body [139].
1781

1782 The nature of SARS-CoV-2 should not be confused with that of other
1783 viruses, such as HIV and HSV. The fact that SARS-CoV-2 has the hardest outer
1784 shell—not only among CoVs but also among all viruses—is a tell-tale sign that
1785 the virus is of a different nature than other viruses such as HSV and HIV-2,
1786 which are known to hide in locations such as the brain only to present
1787 themselves later [109]. HIV and HSV-2 have one of the most disordered outer
1788 shells among viruses, unlike SARS-CoV-2. Their highly disordered outer shells
1789 help them penetrate and hide in organs, as greater disorder allows for more
1790 efficient protein-protein binding. SARS-CoV-2, on the other hand, has one of
1791 the hardest outer shells. If it does not have the benefit of a disordered outer
1792 shell, how does it hide? The answer lies in the mechanism of phagocytosis
1793 described above. There is research showing that inflammatory responses may
1794 be responsible for long COVID. A hard M and inflammatory responses, such as
1795 those caused by cytokines, are not mutually exclusive [142-144]. Due to the
1796 extraordinary hardness of M, SARS-CoV-2 can hide in phagocytes only to appear
1797 whenever the opportunity arises. Whenever the virus keeps reappearing, the immune
1798 system could respond in a manner that could result in inflammation caused by
1799 cytokines.
1800

1801 7.4. Granzymes: A Suspected Mechanism of M Resistance

1802 While the exposure of destructive enzymes has been shown to act against
1803 viruses in the complement system and macrophages, there are also other
1804 destructive enzymes available in the immune system. These involve a family of
1805 enzymes known as granzymes. Upon entry of the virus, the immune system
1806 will initiate a variety of defensive actions that include cytotoxic T-cells and
1807 natural killer (NK) cells, which secrete substances that could potentially
1808 damage viral particles [136-139]. These cells secrete granzymes in response to a
1809 foreign invader. One of the granzymes is perforin, which binds to plasma
1810 membranes and punches holes that allow other granzymes to enter, causing
1811 further damage to the bacterium or infected cell [145]. While current
1812 experimental evidence has shown this to occur in the membranes of bacteria
1813 and infected cells, there is currently no evidence that it damages viral
1814 membranes. Nevertheless, given the known biochemical capabilities of
1815 perforin, perforin can potentially damage the virion in the same manner, since
1816 most animal viruses, including SARS-CoV-2, have a protective outer
1817 membrane layer. In any case, perforin causes lysis in infected cells, thereby
1818 allowing viral particles to be exposed to the complement system and
1819 macrophages. It is also known that, while T-cells and NK cells secrete perforin,
1820 macrophages secrete perforin-2 (PFN2), which is similar to perforin, but it
1821 remains unclear whether PFN2 affects viral membranes directly [144-145].
1822

1823 7.5. Uniqueness of COVID-19 Strategy of Immune Evasion in Long COVID

1824 There are many mysteries involving long COVID that physicians and
1825 scientists are still struggling to solve with respect to creating better treatments.
1826 How does SARS-CoV-2 induce long COVID? What are the mechanisms? Is
1827 there a reservoir? If so, where is it? As we have observed, SDMs offer specific
1828 answers to these questions. While N disorder modulates the amount of virus
1829

1830 replicated, especially in vital organs, the unusually hard M provides resistance
1831 to antimicrobial enzymes. Therefore, the immune evasion strategy used by
1832 SARS-CoV-2 is drastically different from that of viruses such as HIV, HSV, and
1833 HCV [4,16-20,65-67], which have high disorder in the other shell that allows
1834 such viruses to hide in organs. Not only has no comparable high disorder been
1835 detected in SARS-CoV-2, but the virus has one of the hardest outer shells
1836 among viruses—not only among CoVs. This is why phagocytes, such as
1837 macrophages, can serve as a refuge, allowing the virus to dwell and hide in
1838 them. Indeed, one laboratory showed the presence of the virus in the lung
1839 alveolar macrophages of patients who tested negative for the virus in the upper
1840 respiratory system [143]. What is even more puzzling is that several other
1841 laboratories have observed the presence of the virus in many organs of long
1842 COVID patients [111-112]. This raises the following question: Where is the
1843 reservoir? Again, if macrophages and phagocytes are the reservoir, the virus
1844 will be present in various organs since phagocytes are found in nearly every
1845 organ in the body.
1846

1847 7.6. Long COVID, long SARS, and S

1848 Long COVID has been linked to the activation of the immune system via
1849 interferons (IFN- γ) and natural killer T-cells (NK cells), which results in
1850 inflammation [142,144]. Many scientists point to S as the main underlying
1851 cause of the activation. While this postulation is very interesting and plausible,
1852 it raises more questions than it answers. For instance, it does not tell us the
1853 reason why some people experience long COVID while others do not. It does
1854 not tell us whether long COVID arises from a reservoir, and if so, what the
1855 source of the reservoir, i.e., the hiding place of the virus, might be. We also
1856 need to remember that SARS-CoV-1 has a CoV S protein as well. Because the
1857 two viruses are relatively closely related (80%), it is likely the S of both viruses
1858 are functionally similar, including their ability to activate the immune system
1859 in similar ways. A conundrum is, however, observed upon an examination of
1860 the differences between long COVID and long SARS. One stark difference is
1861 the fact that long SARS is usually associated with the severe manifestation of
1862 the disease, whereas long COVID could present itself even with mild
1863 symptoms [64]. How could there be such a disparity if the S proteins of the two
1864 viruses are likely to be structurally similar and when it has been shown that S
1865 activates the immune system [142,144], which is likely to cause long COVID?
1866 SDMs offer a novel explanation. SDMs have observed that SARS-CoV-2 has a
1867 much harder M than that of SARS-CoV-1; as a result, the virus can resist
1868 immune enzymes and hide in the phagocyte in the case of COVID-19. We are,
1869 therefore, likely to obtain a better picture when we consider the roles of M, N,
1870 and S, keeping in mind that N also plays a role, as greater N disorder could
1871 permit the greater production of viral particles—even in the event of long
1872 COVID.
1873
1874

1875 8. Summary and Conclusion

1876 8.1. SDMs: Coherent Links Among Virulence, Infectivity, and Long COVID

1877 This review focuses on three closely related models with respect to
1878 COVID-19. The models use intrinsic protein disorder to link N and M proteins
1879 to infectivity, virulence, and potentially long COVID. While the three models—
1880 shell disorder models (SDMs) [4]—were initially computationally created using
1881 empirical AI molecular techniques based on intrinsic protein disorder,
1882 experimental and clinical data have been examined for the reproducibility and
1883 reliability of SDMs. Interestingly, SDMs are uniquely able to link the major
1884 cause of infectivity, virulence, and potentially long COVID under one coherent
1885 concept of intrinsic protein disorder. An example of the reliability and
1886 reproducibility of SDMs is observed when SDMs were able to provide a novel
1887 and coherent explanation of the differences in virulence and infectivity
1888 between SARS-CoV-1 and SARS-CoV-2, which has been clinically shown to
1889 induce much greater shedding of infectious particles in patients. Curiously, all
1890 known SARS-CoV-2-related viruses, excluding SARS-CoV-1, have an
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1893 abnormally hard outer shell (low M disorder), which is associated with
1894 burrowing animals, such as rabbits and pangolins. Evidence of a unique
1895 molecular and evolutionary relationship (“pangolin footprints”) between
1896 pangolins and COVID-19 has been examined. SDMs suggests that this hard
1897 outer shell is responsible for the high infectivity of COVID-19 and, potentially,
1898 long COVID, as the hard M provides resistance to the antimicrobial enzymes
1899 found in immune and respiratory systems. The implications could provide
1900 clues towards further research involving long COVID and infectivity,
1901 including the search for possible reservoirs among phagocytes. This also
1902 explains clinical observations of the persistence of the virus throughout the
1903 body months after infection. In the case of virulence, greater disorder in N
1904 contributes to more rapid replication by providing more efficient protein-
1905 protein binding. As a result, N disorder correlates with viral titers and,
1906 therefore, virulence; moreover, to a limited extent, it is also correlated with
1907 infectivity. As S (spike protein) is currently yet to be part of SDMs, S is
1908 mentioned sparingly as part of a discussion involving the potentials and
1909 limitations of SDMs.
1910

1911 8.2. Unusual Characteristics in SARS-CoV-2 and the Clinical Manifestations that 1912 Arise from its Evolution

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1914
1915 The phrase “pangolin footprints” refers to a set of molecular signatures
1916 that were left behind by the intimate evolutionary interactions COVID-19
1917 ancestral strains had with pangolins. These signatures—which involve the
1918 abnormally hard M and the trend towards lower N disorder—arose from the
1919 pangolins’ burrowing habit, which entails a harder outer and inner viral shell
1920 to facilitate oral-fecal transmission via buried feces. These features—or
1921 pangolin footprints—are clinically manifested in the symptoms, infectiousness,
1922 and attenuation/virulence of COVID-19. A review of the current knowledge of
1923 immunology indicates that these features are also manifested as long COVID.
1924 The abnormally hard M, which facilitates greater infectiousness by being
1925 resistant to antimicrobial enzymes in the saliva and mucus, can also resist
1926 elimination attempts by the immune system, thus resulting in long COVID.
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1928 8.3. Clues Pointing to Pangolin Footprints in the Evolution of SARS-CoV-2

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1931 A unique and highly unusual property that involves all examined SARS-CoV-2-
1932 related viruses is the hard outer shell (low M PID). This property is very rarely found
1933 even among the CoV family. What is the evolutionary origin of this peculiar
1934 characteristic? A retrospective search of our disorder database of CoVs provided us
1935 with a clue when it was found that very few CoVs have such exceptionally hard M, and
1936 those found were associated with a burrowing animal, such as rabbits. Furthermore, it
1937 can be observed that phylogenetic trees using M have a much closer relationship to
1938 SARS-CoV-2 than previous phylogenetic trees have shown. How can this be possible
1939 when RaTG13 exhibits 96.4% similarity to SARS-CoV-2, whereas pangolin-CoVs
1940 exhibit approximately only 90% similarity to SARS-CoV-2? What is even more
1941 puzzling is that one of our trees shows that Omicron has a closer relationship to
1942 pangolin-CoVs than to other variants. The answer is that phylogenetic algorithms do
1943 not handle recombinations well, and M may be the best choice for phylogenetic studies
1944 since M is abnormally structured (low disorder), which means that it is likely to be
1945 highly conserved. Secondly, many scientists have searched for an intermediary animal
1946 host for SARS-CoV-2, but so far without success. It has obviously not occurred to
1947 many scientists that there is no intermediary animal host because the ancestral virus has
1948 entered and re-entered the human population and other animal populations over a long
1949 period of time, with the primary or secondary reservoir being pangolins. This may
1950 explain why all SARS-CoV-2-related virus have unusually hard M proteins and why
1951 SARS-CoV-2 is highly infectious, not only to humans but also to a wide range of
1952 animals. It takes time for the virus to become highly adapted to such a wide variety of
1953 animals. All these phenomena present clues of a more unique evolutionary relationship
1954 between pangolins and SARS-CoV-2 that needs to be further researched, as there are
1955 hints that the resulting characteristics are related to the behaviors and clinical
1956 manifestations of the virus.

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8.4. Long COVID

As already mentioned above, while current research shows that S is definitely involved in the onset of long COVID [142,144], S does not offer a plausible hypothesis for the underlying cause of long COVID, as the source of the virus reservoir is not addressed. The underlying cause of long COVID has thus far remained a complete mystery, which is a great hindrance to the search for more effective treatments. M and, to a much smaller extent, N proteins via SDMs, however, offer an elaborate and highly plausible explanation using our current knowledge of immunology with respect to the cause of long COVID: The hard outer shell of the virus likely makes it difficult for phagocytes, T-cells, and other entities to eliminate it. As a result, there may be plenty of opportunities for the virus to dwell in phagocytes, which are a likely reservoir.

8.5 Clues for Further Research

We have seen that SDMs offer a novel coherent theory that links virulence and infectivity with N and M via intrinsic protein disorder. Experimental and computational evidence of the reliability and reproducibility [146-147] of SDMs as applied to COVID-19 was examined. We have attempted to show that SDMs using N and M are, by and large, reproducible when experimental and clinical data—especially from other laboratories—are scrutinized. The reason for the reproducibility and reliability of M and N can be partially traced to the abundance of the major proteins and their important roles in the replication process. The role of M in infectivity is based on the observation of an abnormally hard SARS-CoV-2 M using AI. Interestingly, the phylogenetic study of SARS-CoV-2-related viruses points to a closer relationship between pangolin-CoVs and SARS-CoV-2. This has not been shown in any other phylogenetic study using other proteins or entire genomes. While evidence of the reproducibility and reliability of SDMs as applied to COVID-19 using N and M has been presented, further experimental and clinical research is needed to re-affirm their reproducibility and reliability [146-147].

Even though M and N are the most abundant proteins in the virion and cell, respectively, there are 29 CoV viral proteins, of which many are also involved in replication and virulence. For this reason, we have tried to show that many of the limitations of COVID-19 SDMs arise from this fact. A solution would be to include more proteins, such as S and NSP7. This is where further research could help, since current SDMs only incorporate N and M.

While we have argued, using the existing framework of SDMs and current immunological knowledge, that SDMs offer compelling insights into long COVID, their application to this condition is still in its infancy, even if there is evidence that the virus can be detected in the blood and throughout the body, as predicted by SDMs. Given that long COVID is still largely a mystery and an important medical issue, it therefore imperative that long COVID is and continues to be further investigated into using novel tools such as SDMs. Further experimental and clinical studies are therefore necessary, given the clues presented by SDMs.

The clinical implications presented here are numerous. If the virus is hiding in phagocytes only to present itself intermittently, therapeutic strategies, such as antiviral drugs and vaccines, can be tailored to control the sudden release of the virus from its reservoir. Furthermore, SDMs provide novel strategies for vaccine development—not only for SARS-CoV-2 but also other viruses. Moreover, the concept involving virulence and infectivity can be used to monitor the progress of the current COVID-19 pandemic. Thus far, the trend in newer variants is moving towards consistently hard M proteins and lowering N disorder. If this trend continues, SDMs predict that COVID-19 will persist, maintaining high infectivity due to its hard M while presenting milder symptoms arising from its lower M PIDs. In addition, SDMs provide a strategy

for detecting future potential pandemics—not only for CoVs but also other viruses.

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